

Significant current developments in Polish rural law

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Abstract

Le rapport national de la Pologne pour la Commission III au Congrès de la CEDR à Cardiff en 2023 donne, en tant qu'œuvre collective, une image complète des thèmes et des développements du droit agricole.

Der Landesbericht Polens für die Kommission III am CEDR-Kongress in Cardiff 2023 gibt als Gemeinschaftswerk ein umfassendes Bild agrarrechtlicher Themen und Entwicklungen.

1. Organisation and conduct of agricultural activity on a farm

1.1

(1.1.1) Polish legal regulations are still based on concepts fundamental to this branch of law, such as agricultural activity, agricultural holding (farm) and farmer. However, the lack of unification of definitions of the above-mentioned concepts is noticeable. At the level of various acts, the legislator often constructs their definitions, but does so in a differentiated manner depending on the purpose of the specific regulation. By way of example:

Agricultural activity is defined e.g. by the provision of Article 2 of the Act of 11 April 2003 on Shaping the Agricultural System (Journal of Laws of 2022, item 2569) - i.e. a legal act of fundamental importance for the trade in agricultural real estate in Poland. Pursuant to this provision, agricultural activity is production activity in agriculture with respect to plant or animal production, including horticultural, fruit

and fish production. A different definition is provided in Article 21 of the Act of 8 February 2023 on the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027 (Journal of Laws of 2023, item. 412) indicating that the activity consists in: the production of agricultural products by breeding or rearing animals for farming purposes or growing or rearing plants, where agricultural products mean products listed in Annex I to the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), with the exception of fishery products, as well as the cultivation of cotton and short-rotation coppice or the maintenance of agricultural land in a condition that makes it suitable for grazing or cultivation without the need for preparatory measures going beyond the use of normal agricultural methods and normal agricultural equipment. The first of these definitions therefore focuses on the production aspect of the agricultural activity, consisting in the production of agricultural products, while the second also includes the maintenance of agricultural land in a condition suitable for agricultural use without the need for actual production activity. The definition of agricultural activity contained in the Personal Income Tax Act of 26 July 1991 (Journal of Laws of 2022, item 2647) is even more extensive, referring to the biological cycle criterion, thus indicating that agricultural activity also consists in taking care of the biological development of animals and plants for a certain period of time. However, a characteristic feature of the aforementioned definitions is the fact that none of them includes in its scope the post-production stages of the agricultural producer's activity, i.e. processing and commercialisation of agricultural products.

The most important definition of an **agricultural holding** is contained in Article 55³ of the Polish Civil Code, indicating that an agricultural holding is considered to be agricultural land together with forest land, buildings or their parts, equipment and livestock, if they constitute or may constitute an organised economic unit, as well as rights connected with running an agricultural holding. The provision of Article 2 of the aforementioned Act on Shaping the Agricultural System enriches this definition with an object criterion, determining that in such a holding, the area of agricultural land is not less than 1 ha. Both of the above-mentioned definitions thus focus on agricultural land as both a necessary and sufficient component of an agricultural holding. However, the definition contained, for example, in the aforementioned Act on the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027, which refers to the definition contained in Article 3(2) of Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, abstracts from this land definition by pointing out that an agricultural holding is all the components used for agricultural activities and managed by a farmer, located on the territory of the same Member State (in this case the Republic of Poland).

The definition of a **farmer** of fundamental importance -because constitutionally anchored (art. 23 of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland) is contained in art. 6 of the cited Act on Shaping the Agricultural System, pursuant to which an "individual" farmer is regarded as a natural person being the owner, perpetual usufructuary, possessor or leasee of agricultural land whose total area does not exceed 300 ha, having agricultural qualifications and for at least 5 years residing in the commune in the area of which one of the agricultural real estates constituting an agricultural holding is located and personally running this holding for that period. Completely different criteria, in particular not narrowing the scope of the definition to natural persons, are contained in the definition of a farmer contained in the Act on the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027, referring to the definition in Article 3(1) of the cited Regulation (EU) 2021/2115. The latter definition covers a natural or legal person or a group of natural or legal persons, irrespective of the legal status of such group and its members under national law, whose holding is located in an area falling within the territorial scope of application of the Treaties and who carry out an agricultural activity.

An opportunity to eliminate the above-described terminological and semantic discrepancies could be provided by the enactment of the Agricultural Code, the draft of which began discussions in the public forum in December 2022. The presented content of the draft, however, duplicates the above-mentioned definitions of agricultural activity and an agricultural holding contained in the Act on Shaping the Agricultural System and the Civil Code, which are subject to far-reaching criticism in the agrarian literature. The enactment of the Agricultural Code in the current version (at the moment, discussions are already underway on the sixth version of the Code) would contribute to the petrification of this unsatisfactory state of affairs. The new definition of a farmer formulated in the wording of the draft code, according to which a farmer is a person of full age who carries out agricultural activity and manages an agricultural holding as its owner, holder in his/her own right or as a tenant, or co-manages such a holding as a relative, raises a number of further interpretative doubts.

(1.1.2) A characteristic feature of Polish regulations is the fact that the obligation to register with the Central Register of Business Activity and Information - as a prerequisite for undertaking business activity - does not apply to, *inter alia* natural persons conducting production activity in agriculture in the field of agricultural crops and animal husbandry, horticulture, vegetable growing, forestry and inland fisheries; as well as farmers renting rooms, selling home-made meals and providing other services related to tourists' stay on farms; as well as, with significant reservations, farmers selling plant and animal products processed in a manner other than industrially (art. 6 of the Act of 6 March 2018 - Entrepreneurs' Law - Journal of Laws of 2023, item 221.) Organisational units, in particular companies, carrying out this type of activity are, however, subject to registration under general rules in the entrepreneurs' register.

The above remarks indicate that registers do not play a due role in Poland in the framework of public law regulation of agricultural activity, with the reservation of registers of agricultural producer groups and associations of such groups kept by the Agency for the Restructuring and Modernisation of Agriculture on the basis of the Act of 15 September 2000 on Agricultural Producer Groups and Associations of such Groups (Journal of Laws of 2023, item 145) and the register of producers kept by the same institution for the purposes of registering beneficiaries of support under the mechanisms from the funds of the European Union. In the light of the draft Agricultural Code mentioned above, it is proposed to create an additional register of agricultural holdings, apparently for the purposes of agricultural real estate turnover, whose aims and functioning rules, however, remain unclear.

(1.1.3) The regulations on the tax burden of agriculture in Poland have basically remained unchanged for years. Their characteristic feature is the fact that revenues from agricultural activities are, as a rule, not subject to personal and corporate income tax. The most important exception in this respect is revenue from the so-called "special divisions of agricultural production", i.e. in particular cultivation in greenhouses and heated foil tunnels, cultivation of mushrooms and their mycelium, cultivation of "in vitro" plants, farm breeding and rearing of slaughter and laying poultry, poultry hatcheries, breeding and rearing of fur and laboratory animals. Consequently, in practice, the only tax paid by farmers carrying out typical agricultural activities remains "agricultural tax", in which the object of taxation is land, classified in the land and buildings register as "agricultural land". Farmers also benefit from a number of privileges at the level of turnover taxes, i.e. inheritance and donation tax and tax on civil law transactions. In this respect, however, legislative changes in force since 2016 have limited the possibility to benefit from exemptions from these taxes in the case of the acquisition of agricultural land, by introducing the requirement that, as a result of the acquisition, an agricultural holding must be created or enlarged, and the area of the agricultural holding created or enlarged must be not less than 11 ha and

not more than 300 ha, and the holding must have been operated by the acquirer for at least five years from the date of acquisition.

1.2

Over the last few years, the model of public law control of the trade in agricultural real estate in Poland has not changed significantly. The rule still applies that, in principle, agricultural real estate with an area of at least 1 ha may be purchased in Poland (on the basis of any legal event) only with the consent of the Director General of the National Support Centre for Agriculture expressed by way of an administrative decision. Purchasers with the status of an individual farmer and certain other categories of purchasers - e.g. relatives of the seller and heirs in the case of statutory inheritance - are exempt from the obligation to obtain such consent. However, agricultural real estate with an area of at least 0.30 ha and less than 1 ha may be purchased in Poland by anyone, with the proviso that if the purchase is effected on the basis of a sale agreement, the National Support Centre for Agriculture has the right of pre-emption, and in the case of any other legal event - the so-called right to purchase. The purchaser of agricultural real estate is subject to a 5-year obligation to run the agricultural holding which includes the acquired real estate and a prohibition to dispose of or give possession of the real estate to other entities. A characteristic feature of the Polish regulations is, moreover, the fact that subjective changes in commercial companies (both capital companies and partnerships) owning at least 5 ha of agricultural real estate are subject to control. The important practical significance of the above-described regulations contained in the above-mentioned Act on Shaping the Agricultural System is supported by the relatively broad definition of agricultural real estate.

On 13 July 2023, the Act on Amending the Act on Shaping the Agricultural System was passed, which, although it has not yet entered into force, brings some new solutions in the area of public-law control of the trade in agricultural real estate. On the one hand, it eliminates some of the evident absurdities of the hitherto regulations - e.g. the requirement that agricultural real estate may be acquired by prescription only by an individual farmer or the obligation to run an agricultural holding and the prohibition on disposing of real estate despite its being de-regulated in the local zoning plan. On the other hand, the law extends e.g. the previous control of subjective changes in commercial companies also to parent companies of companies owning agricultural real estate.

However, a real revolution in terms of the rules for trading in agricultural real estate would be brought about by the entry into force of the Agricultural Code - should it be enacted. The draft code contains a regulation that, in principle, any agricultural real estate with an area of over 1 ha (regardless of its designation in the local zoning plan and designation in the land and building register) could only be 'acquired' by a 'farmer' or a so-called 'new farmer', in other words access to such real estate would be closed to any organisational units. However, the likelihood of such far-reaching regulations being enacted seems low.

In 2023, the Law of 26 January 2023 on Family Foundations - a piece of legislation of great importance from the point of view of succession planning rules - came into force. Within the scope of activity of this new legal entity, created for the purpose of accumulating property, managing it in the interests of the beneficiaries and fulfilling the benefits for the beneficiaries (thus alluding to the familiar *common law* construction of a *trust*) also lies the production of non-industrially processed plant and animal products, provided that the amount of plant or animal products originating from own cultivation, breeding or rearing, used for the production of a given product constitutes at least 50% of this product. As a result, family foundations have obtained a number of privileges at the level of regulations in the

field of trade in agricultural real estate, although the aforementioned Act of 13 July 2023 amending the Act on Shaping the Agricultural System eliminates the most important of these privileges.

1.3

A characteristic feature of the activities carried out by farmers in Poland is the circumstance that they are mainly carried out by the farmers themselves and their household members. A solution aimed at linking agricultural producers more closely to the economic environment and thus improving the market position of farmers was the introduction of the so-called "farmers' cooperatives", based on the Act of 4 October 2018 on farmers' cooperatives (Journal of Laws of 2018, item 2073). The object of a farmers' cooperative may be, in particular, to carry out business activities in the following areas: storage, packaging and standardisation of products or groups of products, produced by farmers; processing of products or groups of products, produced by farmers, and marketing of the processed products thus obtained; provision of services to farmers related to their production of products or groups of products; disposal of products or groups of products, produced by farmers; and dissemination among its members of environmentally beneficial cultivation methods, production technologies or waste management methods. In addition to the farmers themselves, the members of a farmers' cooperative may also include non-farmers engaged in the storage, warehousing, sorting, packaging or processing of agricultural products or groups of such products, or fish, produced by farmers, or engaged in agricultural support service activities involving the provision of services to farmers, using machinery, tools or equipment used to produce agricultural products or groups of such products, or fish, by these farmers.

A new institution is also the so-called "harvest assistance contract", introduced in the Act of 20 December 1990 on social insurance of farmers (Journal of Laws of 2023, item 208) starting from 18 May 2018. Under it, a 'farmer's helper' undertakes to provide assistance in the harvesting of agricultural products, at a specific place on the farmer's farm and for a specific period of time, and the farmer undertakes to pay the agreed remuneration for the assistance provided. Following the conclusion of that contract, the farmer's helper becomes, to a limited extent, covered by the agricultural social insurance system in Poland, hitherto reserved for farmers and their household members, entitled to certain benefits under that insurance. Indeed, a characteristic feature of the Polish model of agricultural insurance remains the fact that farmers are covered by a separate social insurance system, implemented by a separate institution (the Agricultural Social Insurance Fund and providing for a separate system of benefits and (low) contributions.

There have been no major legislative changes to agricultural property insurance in recent years. Therefore, the system of agricultural property insurance is based on the model of compulsory insurance, which includes insurance of farmers' civil liability for owning an agricultural holding, insurance of buildings constituting an agricultural holding against fire and other fortuitous events, as well as insurance of agricultural crops and livestock. In the case of the latter insurances, a system of premium subsidies for the conclusion of insurance contracts against the risk of the consequences of random events in agriculture is applied - on the basis of the Act of 7 July 2005 on Insurance of Agricultural Crops and Livestock (Journal of Laws of 2019, item 477).

1.4

The source of support for women conducting agricultural activity or undertaking such activity constitute the regulations implementing the Common Agricultural Policy on the territory of Poland. In this

respect, in accordance with the National Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027 and legal acts issued on its basis, preferences for women were introduced at the level of certain mechanisms provided for in this Plan. This concerns, in particular, support for young farmers, undertaking processing activities, development of small farms and creation and development of economic activities under LEADER.

1.5

In recent years, farmers in Poland have been able to receive *de minimis* aid, among others, in the form of: drought aid for farms with less than 30% loss of agricultural production; subsidies for liming; subsidies for certified seed; exemption from civil law transaction tax on the purchase of agricultural land; investment relief in agricultural tax; relief in the payment of social security contributions; relief in the payment of rent for agricultural land to the National Agricultural Support Centre; subsidies for the disposal of fallen livestock; subsidies for the interest on disaster loans; subsidies for the interest on investment loans; subsidies for private forests - support for investments increasing the resilience of forest ecosystems and their value for the environment; subsidies for afforestation and the creation of afforested areas; subsidies for the adaptation of agricultural holdings to the requirements of bio-assurance in the ASF zone. It is worth emphasising that the limits of the cumulative amount of *de minimis* aid in agriculture are very quickly used in Poland.

1.6

(1.6.1-1.6.3) The *Plant Health Law Regulation (EU) 2016/2031* has been implemented in Poland primarily in the Act of 13 February 2020 on the Protection of Plants against Agrophages (Journal of Laws 2023, item 301). This Act determines that all plant health tasks will be performed as before by the authorities of the State Plant Protection and Seed Inspection. The authority that performs checks on compliance with the requirements of Regulation (EU) 2016/2031, as well as checks on the occurrence of agrophages, is the provincial inspector for plant protection and seed. The provincial inspector also issues administrative decisions when the presence of quarantine agrophages or other agrophages subject to compulsory control is found. It is also the competent authority for keeping an official register of professional entities issuing plant passports, with the provincial inspector also retaining this authority. In turn, the Chief Inspector of Plant Protection and Seed Inspection issues permits to conduct research on, *inter alia*, quarantine agrophages, quarantine agrophages for protected zones and plants, plant products or other objects, the introduction of which into Poland or into protected zones is prohibited. A new solution, however, is the possibility of designating areas free of specific agrophages. Such areas may be important in facilitating the export of goods to third countries. The Chief Inspector of Plant Protection and Seed Inspection is the competent authority to designate quarantine stations and isolation facilities. The referred law also contains regulations allowing the State Plant Protection and Seed Inspectorate to carry out its duties with regard to official inspections in the area of plant health, in particular of goods imported from third countries.

The *Animal Health Law Regulation (EU) 2016/429* has not yet been fully implemented in Poland. In this regard, a draft Animal Health and Animal Disease Control Act has been drafted at the Ministry of Agriculture with the aim of introducing the provisions of the regulation into Polish law. According to the plans, the relevant law should be enacted in Q4 2023. The draft act itself implements the provisions of Regulation (EU) 2016/429, in particular by defining: the competence of national authorities

relevant to animal diseases, from the point of view of obligations and powers under the above-mentioned regulation; the principles of animal disease control in a broad sense - to the extent not regulated by the provisions of EU regulations; sanctions for violations of Regulation (EU) 2016/429. In addition, the draft act contains regulations on: animal by-products, non-commercial movement of pets accompanying travellers, monitoring of zoonoses, use of substances with hormonal, thyreostatic and beta-agonist effects, veterinary products for in vitro diagnostics - analogous to the solutions adopted to date.

Pursuant to the proposed regulation, tasks in the area of broadly defined animal disease control will be performed, as they have been so far, by the authorities of the Veterinary Inspection.

In order to implement the *Animal Breeding Regulation (EU) 2016/1012*, the Act of 10 December 2020 on the Organisation of Breeding and Reproduction of Farm Animals (Journal of Laws 2021, item 36) was enacted in Poland. This Act regulates matters concerning the breeding and conservation of genetic resources of livestock, the assessment of their functional value and genetic evaluation, the maintenance of herd books, breeding registers and records, as well as the control of breeding and reproduction of these animals. In addition, the Act identifies the authorities and institutions that will have the powers and competences set out in Regulation (EU) 2016/1012 on the territory of the Republic of Poland. Consequently, the Minister of Agriculture has been given the competence to recognise breeding organisations or other entities that apply for the keeping of herd books and breeding registers for cattle, pigs, sheep, goats and equines as breeding associations and breeding enterprises, to approve breeding programmes carried out by these breeding associations or breeding enterprises, and to impose and revoke the measures set out in Regulation (EU) 2016/1012 in the event that the inspected entities violate the provisions of that Regulation. In turn, the National Animal Breeding Centre carries out official inspections. The law has introduced, following the model of those previously in force, provisions on the principles of keeping herd books and registers, carrying out the assessment of the functional and genetic value and the requirements for animals used for reproduction in order to ensure the continuity of livestock breeding of species such as poultry, fur animals, bees and cervids, which are not affected by Regulation (EU) 2016/1012, and, in addition, in accordance with the demands of breeders, the list of livestock has been supplemented with alpacas and mulberry silkworms in order to allow the breeding of these species to be carried out in the manner previously applicable to livestock. Finally, provisions have been introduced to provide a basis for the granting of state aid for the maintenance of herd books and the assessment of the performance and genetic value of livestock.

1.7

Dualism of legal protection of free-living animals in Poland

(1.6.4 and 1.7) Free-living animals are an integral part of the biosphere and are also subject to legal protection for this reason. Protection in relation to living elements of the biosphere is implemented in Poland through legal instruments for **ideal** (conservation) and **utilitarian** (during economic use) protection. Free-living animals - depending on their species characteristics and threats to their occurrence - are subject to one or the other form of protection. Polish legislation preserves the division into **wild game animals** and **species protected animals** - important from the natural point of view due to the size of the population of these animals and the associated completely different status of protection. This division is also used because of the differentiation of the principles of liability for compensation

for damage caused by these animals (wild game animals – Art. 46 of act of 13.10.1995 Hunting Law¹ and species protected animals – Art. 126 of the act of 16.04.2004 on Nature Protection Act²).

Utilitarian protection was given to free-ranging game animals (synonym: "wild game"). These include **big game** (i.e., elk, deer, wild boar, roe deer, fallow deer, mouflon) and **small game** including both mammals and birds (including: fox, pheasant, partridge, goose, badger and hare. It should be noted that, according to the wording of Art. 2 pr.łow. game animals in their free state are a national asset, and are the property of the State Treasury - regardless of who owns the forest³. On the other hand, animals under **species protection** are animals living in the wild, under strict or partial protection, listed in the list compiled pursuant to Art. 49 u.o.p.⁴ These include, among others: bison, bears, wolves.

Countering the threats posed by African Swine Fever

African swine fever (ASF) is a viral disease caused by a complex DNA virus that affects only one species of large, terrestrial placental mammal of the swine family - wild boars and pigs (*Sus, Sus scrofa*) of all breeds and ages⁵. The disease, which has been spreading for years, has been steadily expanding its range⁶ despite the protective instruments that have been implemented, and is a socio-economic burden on agriculture in many countries, threatening food security and biodiversity and the balance of ecosystems as it affects both breeding and free-living native breeds. Research conducted by EFSA's European Food Safety Authority shows⁷, that since the emergence of ASF genotype II⁸ in the EU in 2014 (in Poland, among others), only 2022 was the first year in which a noticeable decrease of up to 40% in the number of ASF cases in wild boars was observed compared to 2021. (i.e. 12,115 vs. 7,138 cases). This overall decrease is likely due to a reduction in the number of ASF cases in feral pigs in Poland, Germany, Hungary and Slovakia, but a lack of reliability in reporting 9 years after the outbreak cannot be ruled out.

In Poland, we have seen the successive spread of the virus from the eastern to the western border of our country since 2014. In July 2023, the epidemiological status of the occurrence of the threat in the European Union was determined by Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/1485 of

¹ Journal of Law from 2023, item 1082, hereinafter cited as: "pr.łow."

² Journal of Law from 2023, item 1336, hereinafter cited as: "u.o.p."

³ J. Miłkowska, Korzystanie z zasobów zwierzyny łownej [in:] Prawo ochrony środowiska, ed. M. Górski, Warsaw 2021, p. 674, or D. Danecka, W. Radecki, Prawo ówowieckie. Komentarz, Warsaw 2019, pp. 66-72.

⁴ Protected animal species are defined by the provisions of the Decree of the Minister of Environment of 16.12.2016 on the protection of animal species, Journal of Laws from 2022, item 2380.

⁵ D. Beltrán-Alcrudo, M. Arias, C. Gallardo, S.A. Kramer, M.L. Penrith, African Swine Fever: Detection and Diagnosis. A Manual for Veterinarians, FAO Animal Production and Health Manual No. 19, p. 1.

⁶ In January 2022, ASF genotype II was reported on the Italian mainland after an absence of some 40 years. Two new countries also reported the first occurrence of the disease in January: Northern Macedonia and Thailand. In March 2022, ASF was reported for the first time in Nepal. More widely: K. Stahl, A. Boklund, T. Podgóski et al, Epidemiological analysis of African swine fever in the European Union during 2022, Scientific Report of the European Food Safety Authority, EFSA Journal 2023, vol. 21, issue 5, 8016, p. 1-47. doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2023.8016.

⁷ Ibid, p. 25.

⁸ D. Beltrán-Alcrudo, M. Arias, C. Gallardo, S.A. Kramer, M.L. Penrith, African Swine Fever..., p. 7. The first outbreak of the disease was described by R.E. Montgomery, A form of swine fever occurring in British East Africa (Kenya Colony), Journal of Comparative Pathology 1921/34, pp. 159-191. Currently, 23 geographically related genotypes with numerous subgroup genotypes are distinguished. For more information, see M.A. Król, Prevention instruments against African Swine Fever and Legal Protection of Wild Game in Poland [in:] Legal Protection of Animals, ed. E. Kruk, G. Lubeńczuk, H. Spasowska-Czarny, Lublin 2020, pp. 299-300 and the literature indicated therein, and P. Czechowski, Administracyjnyprawne mechanizmy zwalczania Afrykańskiego Pomoru Świń (ASF), "Studia Iuridica" 2020, no. 87, pp. 43-44.

18.07.2023 amending Annexes I and II to Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/605 laying down specific measures for the control of African swine fever⁹. The act confirmed a total of 17 outbreaks of ASF in Poland in July 2023, including several new outbreaks in Wielkopolskie and Mazowieckie Voivodeships, as well as confirmed further outbreaks in restricted areas in Podkarpackie and Lubelskie Voivodeships. This is a major improvement over the several thousand outbreaks reported to the European Commission in several previous years¹⁰.

The virus has spread not only in the eastern and central parts of Poland, but also in the southern (Podkarpackie, Małopolskie provinces) and western (Wielkopolskie, Lubuskie, Dolnośląskie provinces), where the established bans will be applied. The virus also continues to move in our southern neighbors (Slovakia, Czech Republic), and has been in Germany for several years, not only in border Brandenburg or Mecklenburg, but from May 2022 also in Saxony¹¹. The current legal problem is the effective implementation of a set of instruments to prevent the spread of the ASF virus, and thus protect both farmed and free-living animals. In this regard, there is a confluence of the regulation introducing instruments introducing a number of administrative-legal orders related to the protection of animal health (including sanitary culling), or restrictions on agricultural activities in areas where the virus is present and threatened with occurrence, with the regulation on the protection of game animals, which are a national asset in Poland¹².

In Poland, the implementation of EU regulations on the eradication and prevention of infectious diseases in animals and the prevention of risks resulting from this disease to humans is part of the veterinary protection of animals, regulated by the provisions of Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9.03.2016. on transmissible animal diseases and amending and repealing certain acts in the field of animal health ("Animal Health Law")¹³, as well as the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/687 of 17.12.2019 issued on its basis, supplementing Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to provisions on the prevention and control of certain listed diseases¹⁴. Each member state, including Poland, in the event of a confirmed outbreak of a disease, carries out surveillance of the population of these animals, if applicable to a listed disease, and implements the necessary disease prevention and control measures. Member states have also been required to draw up and submit to the Commission an eradication program, continuously monitor and report on its implementation (Art. 31-35 of Regulation 2016/429). Implementing provisions in this regard are contained in Art. 56 of Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/594 of March 16, 2023 laying down specific disease control measures for African swine fever and repealing Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/605¹⁵. National action plans are prepared in accordance

⁹ Official Journal of the EU L 182, p.150.

¹⁰ For example, in 2020 - 4156 ASF outbreaks in wild boars and 103 ASF outbreaks in pigs; in 2021 - 3214 ASF outbreaks in wild boars and 124 ASF outbreaks in pigs; in 2022 - 2113 outbreaks of ASF in wild boars and 14 outbreaks of ASF in pigs. Source: Journal of Law of 2023, item 517.

¹¹ The ASF control strategy for the eastern part of the EU is provided for in document SANTE/7113/2015-Rev7, which provides guidelines for the surveillance and control of African swine fever among feral pigs.

¹² M.A. Król, Prawna ochrona zwierząt łownych a instrumenty zwalczania afrykańskiego pomoru świń, "Studia Iuridica" 2021, No. 88, pp. 187-210.

¹³ Official Journal of the EU L 84 of 2016, p. 1, Consolidated version from 21.04.2021, 002.001.1., hereinafter cited as: "Reg. 2016/429".

¹⁴ Official Journal of the EU L 174 of 2020, p. 64. Current consolidated version from 2023: 03/05/2023, hereinafter cited as: "Reg. 2020/684".

¹⁵ OJ EU L 79 from 17.03.2023, p. 1.

with the minimum requirements set forth in Annex IV, in addition, national plans must take into account local factors, such as the density of pig farms, which may contribute to the spread of the ASF virus. In Poland, an updated **ASF eradication program** is prepared annually, adopted by decree of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development. Currently in force in this regard is the Ordinance of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development dated 1.03.2023 on the introduction in 2023 on the territory of the Republic of Poland of a "Program aimed at early detection of infections with the virus causing African swine fever and expansion of knowledge about the disease and its control"¹⁶, providing for the application of measures aimed at strengthening the protection of the territory of Poland against ASF. The program provides for: 1) reduction of the feral pig population carried out both by hunting and sanitary shooting; 2) removal of potential sources of the ASF virus from the natural environment; 3) carrying out active and passive monitoring in feral pigs and wild boars; 4) activities or investments aimed at prevention, control and eradication of ASF in pigs and wild boars. The program includes measures aimed at combating and preventing the spread of the ASF virus, including, among other things, a ban on feeding feral pigs on the territory of the Republic of Poland. It should also be noted that with the amendment from 2017¹⁷ of the Ordinance of the Minister of the Environment of 16.03.2005 on the determination of hunting periods for game animals¹⁸ it was allowed to hunt wild boars throughout the year, and therefore also sows during the breeding period (§ 1 point 5). These norms were met with a negative response from the public, as well as not fully supported by the PZL¹⁹.

Administrative and legal measures to combat and prevent ASF

Regulation 2016/429 in Title II introduces a catalog of legal instruments that can be used in the event of an outbreak or suspected outbreak of a contagious disease. These include numerous prohibitions, orders and restrictions related to animal husbandry, meat processing and animal transportation. There is also an order for the establishment of special areas: a protection area, a threatened area and a restricted area. A catalogue of legal instruments for disease control in restricted areas is specified in Art. 65 of Regulation 2016/429. In addition, the provisions of Art. 257-262 of Regulation 2016/429 specify emergency measures at the disposal of the competent authorities of the Member States and the European Commission. The powers granted to the Member States include killing, quarantine of animals, isolation, destruction of products, surveillance and identification measures. Based on Art. 63 (4) of Regulation 2020/687, in the event of a suspected infectious disease, including ASF, the competent authorities of the Member State were obliged to notify farmers and hunters, as well as to conduct tests on all shot or dead animals. It is mandatory to designate an infected area with farms under surveillance, and a ban on hunting may also be issued. The competent authority of a Member State is obliged to introduce one or more of such emergency measures when it becomes aware of animals posing a serious risk of spreading a disease on the list of eradicable diseases or the threat of such diseases into the EU. Under the provisions of Regulation 2023/594, in restricted areas, farms, slaughtering and processing plants must be placed under surveillance, and raised animals and pig products, materials or waste that could transmit viruses must not leave the area of the farm (slaughterhouse, plant). Restrictions may also apply to the movement of people or vehicles. Once a disease outbreak is

¹⁶ Consolidated text from 2023, Journal of Laws, p. 517.

¹⁷ Ordinance of the Minister of Environment of 1.08.2017 amending the Ordinance on hunting periods for game animals, Journal of Laws, p. 1487.

¹⁸ Consolidated text from Journal of Laws from 2023, p. 99.

¹⁹ Statement of the General Board of the PZL, 10.01.2019, <https://wiadomosci.onet.pl/kraj/mysliwi-przeciwni-strzelaniu-do-ciezarnych-loch-oswiadczenie-pzl-i-nrl/0sn4dpcb> (accessed September 21, 2019). For more on this topic, see M.A. Król, Prawna ochrona zwierząt..., pp. 204-205.

established on a farm, with a few exceptions, the slaughter of all pigs and the destruction of infected meat or other waste is required. Similar rules apply to the detection of the disease in a slaughterhouse or means of transportation.

In Poland, the eradication and prevention of infectious diseases in animals and the prevention of risks arising to humans is part of the veterinary protection of animals, regulated, as a rule, by the provisions of the Law of 11.03.2004 on the protection of animal health and eradication of infectious diseases in animals²⁰ and the Law of 20.12.2019 on amending certain laws to facilitate the eradication of infectious diseases in animals²¹. Regulation in this area is also regulated in the provisions of the Law on Hunting. Sanitary and veterinary law²² - both EU and national - essentially constitutes a complex of regulations aimed at safeguarding the penetration of animal diseases into livestock communities. The above regulations also apply to the control and elimination of zoonotic diseases that can transmit to humans. The sanitary-veterinary legal norms use the sovereign forms of action, in which orders, prohibitions or mixed constructions predominate²³. The legal regulations in force in Poland serve to introduce instruments aimed at: **1) prevention and eradication and ASF; 2) adoption of special legal solutions related to the occurrence of ASF on the territory of Poland.**

The first group of instruments are those for preventing and combating ASF. In this regard, the legislator introduces an administrative-legal requirement that is a kind of complex of orders, prohibitions and permits. As indicated in Art. 2(27) u.z.z. the control of contagious animal diseases involves a variety of measures, such as reporting, preventing further spread, detection, control and eradication of contagious animal diseases, cleaning and decontamination, as well as the handling of the reintroduction of animals to the farm. The analysis made makes it possible to list several groups of duties:

1) The **signaling order** under Article 42(1)(1) u.z.z., in the case of a suspected outbreak of disease, imposes an order on the animal keeper to immediately notify the veterinary inspection authorities, the veterinarian or the municipal executive body. In addition, the obligation to notify the indicated authorities or the nearest animal clinic of perceived symptoms of diseases of free-living animals rests, based on Art. 14 pr.łow. with the lessee and manager of the hunting circuit and owners, holders and managers of land. Due to the nature of the spread of ASF beyond the borders of the country, in the event of an outbreak of diseases, the veterinary surveillance authorities provide information on the infected, endangered or other areas established in connection with the eradication of the disease extending beyond the borders of the Republic of Poland to the competent authorities of EU member states or third countries in order to cooperate in the eradication of the infectious disease of animals (Art. 48 u.z.z.). Ordinance of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 6.05.2015 on the eradication of African swine fever²⁴ specifies the manner and procedure for dealing with suspicion and confirmation of ASF, the manner and conditions for defining infected, endangered and contaminated areas, the measures used to combat the disease, the manner of cleaning and disinfection and re-housing of animals.

2) **administrative-legal instruments of an obligatory-regulatory nature.** The minister responsible for agriculture may, by decree, introduce: a) the division of the country into restricted and disease-free

²⁰ Consolidated text from 2023 Journal of Law, p. 1075, hereinafter: u.z.z.

²¹ Journal of Law from 2020, p. 148.

²² M. Rudy, *Wstęp do prawa sanitarnego i weterynaryjnego*, Warsaw 2016, p. 98.

²³ P. Czechowski, *Administracyjnoprawne mechanizmy...*, pp. 43-44; M.A. Król, *Prawna ochrona zwierząt...*, pp. 202-206.

²⁴ Journal of Law from 2015, p. 754.

zones, and may furthermore order widespread testing, treatment and other procedures on animals of susceptible species, with a view to preventing the uncontrolled spread of an infectious animal disease; b) temporary bans on leaving an outbreak and temporary restrictions on the movement of people or vehicles, with a view to preventing the uncontrolled spread of infectious animal diseases and minimizing the inconvenience of the restrictions introduced (Art. 47 (1) and (2) u.z.z.). In addition, under Art. 44-46 u.z.z., injunctions and prohibitions may be imposed, established by the district veterinarian both by regulation (local act) and administrative decision or by decree of the governor. In this form, **an order for sanitary shooting of game animals** (wild boars) imposed on lessees or managers of hunting districts 46(3)(8) and 47a u.z.z.²⁵, including in areas covered by legal forms of nature protection and in their buffer zones, may be established. Pursuant to Art. 49 u.z.z., the holder of animals killed or slaughtered by order of the Veterinary Inspection authorities, or where the animals died as a result of treatments ordered by these authorities in the control of contagious animal diseases, is entitled to compensation, provided that he has complied with all the obligations ordered in connection with ASF²⁶.

In addition, under Art. 45(1)(8c) and Art. 46(3)(8d) u.z.z. as amended in 2019²⁷, the possibility has been established to impose orders on public road managers to: close animal crossings located in road lanes, carry out technical obstacles, in particular the construction of fences or technical protection, or lay disinfectant mats, and maintain them after laying them in a condition that ensures the effective action of the disinfectant. On the other hand, forest inspectors may be ordered to construct fences in a certain area to restrict or stop the migration of animals from forest areas (Art. 46(3)(8) u.z.z.).

The existing administrative-legal instruments of an obligatory-regulatory nature are supplemented by another one, allowing, under Art. 11 (4-5) u.z.z., the use of the assistance of uniformed services (police, border guards, state fire departments) or veterinary inspection authorities in securing the hunting area, searching for fallen animals, or controlling compliance with the rules of bioassurance in carrying out the shooting.

The second group of administrative-legal instruments is associated with the introduction of special legal solutions related to the occurrence of ASF on Polish territory. As indicated in the doctrine²⁸, the efficiency of animal production depends largely on the health safety of individual animals, which refers both to the genetic material and the animals traded. The development of trade in animals and food products of animal origin and the migration of disease vectors have created enormous opportunities for the spread of these infectious animal diseases around the world²⁹. Therefore, ASF is the cause of

²⁵ This is provided for by the provisions of the Decree of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 19.02.2016 on the Order of Sanitary Shooting of Wild Boars, Journal of Laws, item 229, ordering the sanitary shooting of wild boars to achieve a wild boar population density of at most 0.5 individuals/km² in the areas specified in the Annex to the Decree, excluding national parks and nature reserves.

²⁶ Specific issues are regulated by the Decree of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development dated 10/08/2021 on measures to be taken in connection with the occurrence of African swine fever, Journal of Laws item 1485, on the basis of which prohibitions and orders were established for farms in areas where the disease is present and threatened.

²⁷ Art. 45(1)(8c) u.z.z., as amended by Art. 5(1)(a) of the 2019 Amendment Act.

²⁸ I. Lipińska, Zwalczenie chorób zakaźnych zwierząt gospodarskich – wybrane aspekty prawne, "Studia Iuridica Agraria" 2017/XV, p. 157.

²⁹ Z. Gliński, K. Kostro, Choroby zakaźne zwierząt z elementami epidemiologii i zoonoz, Warsaw 2011, p. 11.

significant economic losses borne not only by pig farmers³⁰ and the state budget³¹, related to the complete blocking of the possibility of exporting pigs or pork meat to third countries, but also the inability to trade animals and products of animal origin within the EU. For these reasons, there was a need to ensure the possibility of managing products of animal origin for human consumption produced in areas where restrictions have been imposed due to the outbreak of this virus. Special solutions, concerning the supply of pork from farms located in areas subject to rationing measures, were normalized by the Law of 5.09.2016 on special solutions related to the occurrence of African swine fever on the territory of the Republic of Poland³². The legislation introduces procedural facilitations for the disposal of pork for producers from areas where the virus is present, provided that it meets veterinary requirements, confirmed by multiplied inspection. Breeders in ASF-affected areas can also receive financial support for improving herd genetic material and for changing the profile of agricultural production, or compensation for losses incurred when reselling animals³³.

Existing regulations are proving inadequate, and the virus is spreading steadily. This is influenced by a number of factors, including the degree of awareness of bioassurance principles among farmers and hunters. The Supreme Audit Office (NIK) in 2017, in the information on the results of the audit "Implementation of the bioassurance program as an element of the control of African swine fever"³⁴ critically evaluated the bioassurance program conducted in 2015-2017, as the supervision of the Chief Veterinarian and the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development over the preparation of the program and its implementation. CSO data³⁵ shows a reduction of almost 75% of the feral boar population over the past seven years, indicating the adoption of sanitary shooting as an essential measure to combat the disease. Still, wild boars, as game animals, are an object of legal protection, as stipulated by the provision of Article 2 of the Hunting Law, a national asset, and by virtue of Article 323(2) of the Environmental Protection Law³⁶ a structural element of the environment as a common good.

Legal basis in hunting law

Hunting and hunting management are addressed by the provisions of several EU normative acts. These include: 1) Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council (EU) 2021/555 of 24.03.2021 on control of the acquisition and possession of weapons³⁷, which regulates the possession of hunting

³⁰ There are increased costs of keeping animals on the farm, higher production costs, deterioration of growth. More widely: I. Lipińska, Nadzwyczajne środki wsparcia jako prawna ochrona unijnego rynku rolnego, "Przegląd Prawa Rolnego" 2017/1, p. 91.

³¹ They are related, among other things, to the costs of eradication, payment of compensation, and, most importantly, suspension of marketing and export of pigs and foodstuffs produced from pork meat. More widely: A. Nowak, I. Nowak, Afrykański pomór świń jako choroba zakaźna – wybrane aspekty prawne, „Przegląd Prawa Publicznego” 2020/11, pp. 19-36.

³² Journal of Laws 2021, item 1573, along with implementing acts to this law.

³³ More extensively on this subject I. Lipińska, Nadzwyczajne środki..., pp. 91-92.

³⁴ KRR 430.006,2017. Najwyższa Izba Kontroli NIK highlighted the ineffectiveness of the measures taken due to inadequate preparation of the program and its unreliable implementation. Farmers did not comply with the rules governing the proper anti-epizootic protection of farms, veterinary inspection inspections of farms were unreliable (which may have been influenced by the insufficient number of doctors employed in district veterinary inspectorates in relation to the scope of their tasks), and supervision of the program's implementation by the Chief Veterinary Officer and the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development was insufficient.

³⁵ GUS, Rocznik Statystyczny Leśnictwa 2021, p. 161. In 2015, the wild boar population was 264.8 thousand, and in 2021. - 67.9 thousand.

³⁶ Act of 27.04.2001. - Environmental Protection Law, consolidated version Dz. U. of 2022, p. 2556 as amended.

³⁷ OJ EU L 115, p. 1.

weapons³⁸; 2) Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21.05.1992. on the protection of natural habitats and wild fauna and flora³⁹, which in Article 14 allows in areas of special environmental protection the extraction from the wild of fauna species, as well as their exploitation; 3) Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30.11.2009 on the protection of wild birds⁴⁰, which in Art. 7 (4) and Art. 8 (1) and (2) establishes a ban on hunting birds during their breeding period and on migratory birds; 4) Regulation (EC) No. 853/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29.04.2004 laying down specific hygiene rules for food of animal origin⁴¹, which establishes rules for the control of hunted game placed on the market in the EU⁴². The norms contained in the EU acts require implementation in the member states. For the rest of the matter, hunting issues remain an internal matter of each country and are subject to national regulations.

Harmonizing hunting with the directions of agricultural land use in Poland

Rural areas are an area of coexistence of farming, forestry and hunting. Nowadays, intensive, often industrialized agricultural activity causes many threats to native nature in rural areas, has a direct impact on the state of biosphere elements. The literature lists many factors that cause degradation of natural values, and at the same time cause depletion of biodiversity⁴³. This is counteracted by usable instruments of biosphere protection in agriculture, forestry and hunting. In Poland, the legislator indicates the necessity of harmonizing hunting with the directions of agricultural, forestry and fishing land use. According to the wording of Art. 11 of the hunting pr. hunting shall be carried out in accordance with the **basic directions of use of agricultural, forestry and fishing areas**, under conditions of constant improvement of the animal's habitat. This does not mean subordination of hunting to these types of management, but **a directive to those involved in hunting, ordering that hunting be organized in such a way that it does not conflict with rational agricultural, forestry and fishing management**⁴⁴. Hunting should not conflict with agricultural management, and as stated in the doctrine⁴⁵ - in case of unavoidable collisions, priority should be given to agricultural, forestry, fishing management. The concept of rational agricultural management has not been defined in our legislation. Nowadays, the term "rational **agricultural management**" should be understood as rational economic activities of the agricultural producer, agricultural management based on modern scientific methods, principles and technologies, indicated as good agricultural practices and meeting the requirements of cross-compliance, in accordance with the principles of environmental protection. This term should be referred to such a

³⁸ The implementation of the directive is expressed in the provisions of the Law of 21.05.1999 on arms and ammunition (Journal of Laws of 2020, p. 955, as amended). See more extensively B. Kurzępa, *Ustawa o broni i amunicji. Komentarz*, Warsaw 2010; S. Maj, *Ustawa o broni i amunicji. Komentarz*, Warsaw 2010, pp. 16-17.

³⁹ OJ EC L 206, p. 7 as amended.

⁴⁰ OJ EU L 20, p. 7, as amended.

⁴¹ OJ EU L 139, p. 55, as amended. More see: R. Stec, *Prawo łowieckie. Wybrane aspekty prawno-porównawcze*, Warsaw 2009, pp. 37-47; R. Stec, *Dostosowanie polskiego prawa łowieckiego do prawa Unii Europejskiej, "Łowiec Polski" 1999/9, passim.*

⁴² The implementation of the regulation is expressed in the provisions of the Law of 16.12.2005 on products of animal origin, i.e., OJ 2023, p. 872, and the Decree of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 21.03.2016 on the detailed conditions for recognition of marginal, local and limited activities (Journal of Law, p. 451).

⁴³ B. Poskrobko, T. Poskrobko, K. Skiba, *Ochrona biosfery...*, p. 178.

⁴⁴ See W. Radecki, *Prawo łowieckie. Komentarz*, Warsaw 2010, p. 49.

⁴⁵ D. Danecka, W. Radecki, *Prawo łowieckie...*, pp. 133-134.

way of farming that does not contradict the conservation objectives established in the prescribed form in the area⁴⁶.

By the Law of March 22, 2018 amending the Law of Hunting and certain other laws⁴⁷, the provisions of Art. 11(2)(4) and (5) pr.łow., which required, when managing game populations, the rational use of chemicals in agriculture and forestry, and the appropriate use of timing (e.g., field work) and agrotechnical techniques that do not endanger the existence of game in the area, were repealed. These norms clearly emphasized the need to take care of wildlife also during agricultural activities, and their repeal does not correspond with the content of Article 1 of the hunting law. Instead, the provision of Art. 11(2)(7) pr.łow. was maintained, stating that the management of game populations requires the realization of the main economic objectives in agriculture, fishing and forestry, which emphasizes the primacy of economic considerations over ecological ones.

What – according to the provisions of the current law – should agricultural management be in order to be considered rational? It should be noted that the authorization of the use of plant protection products or the marketing of these products, fertilizers or plant growing aids is subject to strict legal regulation. The legislator mandates the rational use of plant protection products (in accordance with the Law of 8.03.2013 on plant protection products⁴⁸) and fertilizers (in accordance with the Law of 10.07.2007 on fertilizers and fertilization⁴⁹). Only those agents that, when used properly and in accordance with their intended purpose, do not pose a threat to human health, animal health or the environment may be authorized for use and marketing⁵⁰. As W. Radecki⁵¹, this means, among other things, the order to follow - in addition to the statutory regulations - the instructions for use provided by the manufacturer. The set of rules that will apply in determining the scope of the term "rational farming" are the *cross-compliance* requirements, which consist of the obligations set forth in Art. 93 and Annex II of Regulation 1306/2013 on the financing of the Common Agricultural Policy⁵², and in the new programming period of the Common Agricultural Policy, the conditionality requirements (conditionality) set forth in sec. conditionality) set out in Section 2 and Annex III of the EU Parliament and Council Regulation 2021/2115 laying down provisions on support for strategic plans drawn up by Member

⁴⁶ M.A. Król, *Racjonalna gospodarka rolna na obszarach objętych prawnymi formami ochrony przyrody*, "Studia Iuridica Agraria" 2011/IX, p. 320.

⁴⁷ Journal of Laws, p. 651.

⁴⁸ Consolidated version Journal of Law of 2023, p. 340 as amended.

⁴⁹ Journal of Law 2023, p. 569.

⁵⁰ A list of fertilizers and plant growing aids that can be marketed on the basis of permits from the minister responsible for agriculture, pursuant to Art. 8 (1) and (2) on fertilizers and fertilization can be found on the website of the office serving the minister responsible for agriculture and rural development: <https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo/wykaz-nawozow-i-srodkow-wspomagajacych-uprawe-roslin>.

⁵¹ W. Radecki, *Prawo łowiecki...*, p. 119.

⁵² Regulation (EU) No. 1306/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17.12.2013 on the financing, management and monitoring of the common agricultural policy and repealing Council Regulations (EEC) No. 352/78, (EC) No. 165/94, (EC) No. 2799/98, (EC) No. 814/2000, (EC) No. 1290/2005 and (EC) No. 485/2008 (OJ EU L 347, p. 549, as amended).

States under the common agricultural policy (CAP strategic plans) and financed by the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD)⁵³. In Poland, these requirements have been specified in implementing regulations⁵⁴.

In 2018, the legislator repealed the norm in Art. 11(2)(5) pr.łow. addressed to farmers, which obliged them to use agrotechnical terms and techniques that do not endanger the livelihood of animals. Such rules relating to agrotechnical terms and techniques are not common in our legislation. However, they were provided for, among others, by the measures of agri-environment-climate programs, established on the basis of Art. 28 of Regulation 1305/2013⁵⁵. This provision introduced basic rules for the implementation of agri-environment-climate measures, which are aimed at preserving and promoting good agricultural practices for the protection of the most valuable natural habitats. This is especially true for Package 4 "Valuable habitats and endangered bird species in Natura 2000 areas" and Package 5 "Valuable habitats outside Natura 2000 areas"⁵⁶. Their inclusion in the RDP is mandatory at the national or regional level, however voluntary for farmers.

Liability for damage caused by free-living animals

Free-living animals in rural areas cause damage that creates a conflict of interest between the goals of usable biosphere protection and agricultural activities. This is to be counteracted by provisions on compensation liability for free-living animals.

Liability for damage caused by animals under legal species protection by, among others, the **wolf**, was established for the benefit of the State Treasury in the Law on Nature Protection, and this liability covers damage that has been defined both as to the type and species of animal causing the damage. According to Art. 126(1) u.o.p. the State Treasury is liable for damage caused by: bison, **wolves**, lynx, bears and beavers⁵⁷. The above catalogue is not closed - the Council of Ministers has the right by decree to designate also other protected animal species for which the State Treasury will be liable.

Liability for damage caused by wild game animals is borne **by**: (1) the lessee or manager of the hunting district in two categories of damage: (i) damage caused to crops and crops by wild boar, elk, deer, fallow deer and roe deer; (ii) damage caused in the course of hunting. In the practice of applying

⁵³ OJ L 435, 6.12.2021, p.1.

⁵⁴ Ordinance of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of March 9, 2015 on standards for good agricultural practices compatible with environmental protection (Journal of Laws, p. 344, as amended), which introduced, among other things, several attitudes relating to the principles of fertilizer use. In the new programming perspective, these requirements are set forth in the Law of February 8, 2023 on the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027, Journal of Laws of 2023, p. 412.

⁵⁵ Regulation (EU) 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17.12.2013 on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No. 2005/1698 (OJ EU L 347, p. 487, as amended).

⁵⁶ Packages provided for under the "Agri-environment-climate measure" - included in the Rural Development Program 2014-2020, approved by the European Commission Decision 2014PL06RDNP001, version 12.0 of 18.02.2022.

⁵⁷ On the content of the provision in connection with the decisions of the Constitutional Court: D. Danecka, W. Radecki, Ustawa o ochronie przyrody. Komentarz, Warsaw 2018, pp. 611-612.

the law, the term "agricultural crop" has raised doubts. The courts have adopted both a narrow interpretation⁵⁸, as a result of which, for example, an orchard crop was denied the character of an agricultural crop, and a broad interpretation⁵⁹, as a result of which an agricultural crop within the meaning of Art. 46(1)(1) pr.łow. was considered any crop grown on agricultural land, which is the result of human activity and not natural factors, which are closely related to the productive function of the land⁶⁰; 2) the State Treasury in two situations: (i) damage to crops and crops caused in the course of hunting by game animals under year-round protection, which in today's state of the law applies only to moose⁶¹; in forestry districts, compensation is paid by the State Forests from the funds of the state budget, and field districts and outside hunting districts - the provincial board from the funds of the state budget; (ii) damage to crops and crops caused outside hunting districts, that is, in national parks and reserves; compensation is then paid by the provincial board from state budget funds.

The rules and procedures for estimating hunting damage are defined by the provisions of Art. 46 (2-8), Art. 46a-46g pr.łow. and the 2019 Executive Order.⁶² Owners or holders of agricultural and forest land should, as required, cooperate with tenants and managers of hunting districts in protecting land from damage caused by game. Damage estimation, as well as the determination of the value of compensation, is carried out by a team consisting of a representative of the provincial centre for agricultural advisory services, a representative of the lessee or manager of the hunting district, the owner or holder of agricultural land where the damage occurred. Damage estimation consists of visual inspection and final estimation, except that in the case of damage to crops, damage caused by wild boars on meadows and pastures and damage to crops, if the damage occurred and was reported immediately before or during the equipment, only final estimation is carried out.

In accordance with Art. 48 pr.łow., payment of compensation was excluded in several cases, including to owners of damaged crops or crops who did not consent to the construction of facilities or performance of damage prevention measures by the lessee or manager of the hunting district, for damage not exceeding the value of 100 kg of rye per hectare of crop, or for damage to crops deposited in heaps, piles and mounds in.

2. Position of farmers in the value chain, cooperatives, organisations, contracts and agri-food law

2.1

Counteracting the unfair use of contractual advantage in the trade of agricultural and food products in Poland

⁵⁸ Judgment of the Supreme Court of 4.07.2002, I CKN 795/00, LEX No. 56890.

⁵⁹ Among others, the resolution of the Supreme Court of 14.04.1994, III CZP 46/94, LEX No. 4057; the judgment of the Supreme Court of 20.01.2005, II CK 361/04, LEX No. 148660; and above all the resolution of the Supreme Court(7) of 27.11.2007, III CZP 67/07, LEX No. 316085.

⁶⁰ More extensively: B. Rakoczy, *Odpowiedzialność za szkody łowieckie*, Warsaw 2016, pp. 99-101.

⁶¹ D. Danecka, W. Radecki, *Prawo łowieckie...*, p. 414.

⁶² Ordinance of the Minister of Environment dated 16.04.2019 on detailed conditions for estimating damage to crops and crops, *Journal of Laws*, p. 776.

In Poland, Directive (EU) 2019/633 of the European Parliament and of the Council on unfair trading practices in business-to-business relationships in the agricultural and food supply chain was implemented by the Act of 17 November 2021 on Counteracting Unfair Exploitation of Contractual Advantage in the Trade in Agricultural and Food Products.⁶³ However, this was not the first act regulating this issue. Prior to the entry into force of the Directive, the Act of 15 December 2016 on Counteracting the Unfair Use of Contractual Advantage in the Trade of Agricultural and Food Products had been in force from 12 July 2017.⁶⁴ It was repealed on 23 December 2021 with the entry into force of the new act implementing the Directive. Despite the same title, the new act differs from the previous regulation.

The definition of agricultural and food products was expanded. The previous act referred in this matter to the definition of food within the meaning of Article 2 of Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law,⁶⁵ whereas the current regulations refer to products listed in Annex I to the TFEU,⁶⁶ as well as products not listed in this Annex but processed for consumption using products listed in this Annex. Thus, the amendment to the definition extended the application of the provisions of the Act to animal feed, live animals, seeds and oleaginous fruits.

The definition of a purchaser has also been modified. A purchaser is now understood to be an entrepreneur or an entity referred to in Article 4 of the Act of 11 September 2019 – Public Procurement Law,⁶⁷ which directly or indirectly purchases agricultural or food products from a supplier. The previous act defined a purchaser only as an entrepreneur who directly or indirectly acquires agricultural or food products from a supplier for the purpose of sale, resale or processing, whereas the new act, by reference to the Public Procurement Law, also applies to public entities.

The legal definition of contractual advantage remained unchanged, which, according to the Act, should be understood as the existence of a significant disproportion in the economic potential between a purchaser and a supplier or a supplier and a purchaser. Both Acts introduced a prohibition on the exploitation of contractual advantage between a purchaser and a supplier and between a supplier and a purchaser. In both regulations, the exploitation of contractual advantage is considered unfair if it is contrary to good customs and threatens or prejudices a substantial interest of the other party. In both the previous and current legislation, the catalogue of unfair exploitation of advantage is open. The previous legislation listed 4 examples of unfair exploitation of advantage. In the current legislation, the legislator has identified 17 such practices, whereby 11 practices are absolutely prohibited and 6 practices are allowed provided that they have been clearly and unequivocally agreed upon in the contract between a purchaser and a supplier prior to their use. Significantly, when assessing the examples of unfair practices listed *expressis verbis* by the legislator, no consideration is given to the prerequisites of contradicting good customs and jeopardising or infringing the significant interest of the other party.

⁶³ Consolidated text: Journal of Laws 2023, items 351 and 852.

⁶⁴ Consolidated text: Journal of Laws 2020, item 1213.

⁶⁵ Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety (OJ L 31, 1. February 2002).

⁶⁶ Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (Official Journal of the EU C 326/43 of 26 October 2012).

⁶⁷ Act of 11 September 2019 - Public Procurement Law (consolidated text: Journal of Laws 2022, item 1710, as amended).

This leads to the conclusion that the examples listed by the legislator already in themselves prove unfair exploitation of contractual advantage.

In addition, unlike in the previous legislation, the new Act defines what constitutes a significant disproportion in economic potential in the case of unfairly exploitative contractual advantage practices used by a purchaser against a supplier and vice versa by introducing legal presumptions. These presumptions reverse the burden of proof to the party against whom proceedings for unfairly exploitative contractual advantage practices are conducted, which will contribute to a more effective implementation of the Act.

Both under the current and the previous legislation, an administrative model of establishing violations of the Act was adopted. The President of the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection remained the competent authority in this matter. It should be emphasised that the protection against practices unfairly exploiting contractual advantage in the trade in agricultural or food products provided for in the Act does not exclude protection under other acts. Thus, aggrieved entities have not been deprived of the possibility to pursue claims on a civil basis under the provisions of the Civil Code,⁶⁸ the Act on Combating Unfair Competition⁶⁹ and the Act on Counteracting Excessive Delays in Commercial Transactions.⁷⁰ Also, the President of the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection has been given the competence to present a significant view to the court in cases of civil law claims related to practices by suppliers towards purchasers or by purchasers towards suppliers that may constitute practices which unfairly exploit contractual advantage.

Proceedings on unfair contractual advantage practices are initiated *ex officio*. Proceedings are not initiated if two years have elapsed since the end of the year in which the unfair practices ceased. The initiation of proceedings may be preceded by a preliminary investigation if the circumstances indicate a possible violation of the provisions of the Act. The aim of the preliminary investigation is, in particular: to determine whether there has been an infringement of the provisions of the Act justifying the initiation of proceedings in the case and to examine the market. Anyone may notify the President of the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection of a suspected practice of unfairly exploiting a contractual advantage. The notification should contain an indication of the entity alleged to use unfair practices, a description of the facts, evidence of a probable infringement of the provisions of the Act, the scope of information not to be disclosed in the course of the proceedings and data identifying the notifying person. The notification must be accompanied by documents which may provide evidence of a violation of the Act. The identity of the notifying person are not disclosed to the parties to the proceedings at any stage of the proceedings and after its completion, unless the notifying person consents to it. The preliminary investigation should not last longer than four months, and in particularly complicated cases not longer than five months from the date of their initiation. The investigation procedure is initiated by the President of the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection *ex officio* by way of a decision. The termination of such proceedings also takes place by way of a decision.

A party to the proceedings on practices unfairly exploiting contractual advantage is anyone against whom the proceedings have been initiated. The President of the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection issues a decision on the initiation of the aforementioned investigation and notifies the party

⁶⁸ Act of 23 April 1964 - Civil Code (consolidated text: Journal of Laws 2022, item 1360, as amended).

⁶⁹ Act of 16 April 1993 on Combating Unfair Competition (consolidated text: Journal of Laws 2022, item 1233).

⁷⁰ Act of 8 March 2013 on the Counteracting Excessive Delays in Commercial Transactions (uniform text: Journal of Laws 2023, item 711, as amended).

to the investigation. President of the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection has been granted the competence to:

- 1) demand the provision of information, including the provision of documents on practices which unfairly exploit contractual advantages;
- 2) carry out an inspection;
- 3) to commission the Trading Standards Association to carry out an inspection or carry out other activities falling within its scope of action.

In matters not regulated by the Act, the provisions of the Code of Administrative Procedure are applied to proceedings before the President of the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection,⁷¹ whereas in matters concerning evidence, to the extent not regulated by the Act, the provisions of the Code of Civil Procedure are applicable.⁷² The proceedings should be concluded no later than within five months of their initiation. Prior to the conclusion of the proceedings, the President of the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection may propose, *ex officio* or at the request of a party, to enter into a procedure of voluntary submission to a financial penalty, if the application of this procedure contributes to the acceleration of the proceedings. In the case of voluntary submission, the financial penalty shall be reduced by no more than 50% in relation to the financial penalty that would have been imposed without voluntary submission. The voluntary submission procedure was not provided for in the previous Act.

The President of the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection issues a decision declaring a practice to be a practice unfairly exploiting contractual advantage if he or she finds a breach of the prohibition of the practice. In the decision, the President of the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection orders the abandonment of the practice imposing the prohibition if the practice has not been abandoned by the time the decision is issued, and may impose on a supplier or purchaser a financial penalty of no more than 3% of the turnover achieved in the financial year preceding the year in which the penalty is imposed, if the supplier or purchaser, even if unintentionally, committed a breach of the prohibition. In addition, the President of the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection may, in the course of the proceedings, before issuing a decision concluding the case, by way of a decision:

- 1) oblige the party to take or refrain from taking certain actions to cease the infringements or to remedy their effects, and set a time limit for doing so;
- 2) oblige the party to remedy the infringement and set a time limit for the remedy;
- 3) oblige the party to discontinue certain actions in order to prevent serious and difficult to remedy damage to the supplier or the purchaser, together with a time limit for the duration of the decision – no longer than until the decision concluding the proceedings in the case.

Decisions issued by the President of the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection may be appealed to the Regional Court in Warsaw – Court of Competition and Consumer Protection within one month from the date of their delivery. Entities whose rights have been violated in the course of

⁷¹ Act of 14 June 1960 – Code of Administrative Procedure (uniform text: Journal of Laws 2023, item 775).

⁷² Act of 17 November 1964 – Code of Civil Procedure (uniform text: Journal of Laws 2021, item 1805, as amended).

the inspection have the right to lodge a complaint to the Regional Court in Warsaw – Court of Competition and Consumer Protection against inspection activities going beyond the subject-matter of the inspection or other inspection activities undertaken in violation of the regulations within 7 days from the date of the activity.

2.2

Cooperatives in agriculture in Poland

Cooperative Law⁷³ defines a cooperative as a voluntary association of an unlimited number of persons, with variable membership and a variable share fund, which carries out joint economic activity in the interests of its members. A special type of cooperative in Polish law remains an agricultural production cooperative, the object of which is to run a common farm and activities for the benefit of individual farms of its members, and a cooperative may carry out other economic activities. Cooperative Law also distinguishes cooperatives of agricultural associations, whose subject of activity is the provision of services for agriculture and other types of services resulting from the needs of the rural environment. They may also engage in the production of agricultural materials, agricultural processing and agricultural production (farming).

According to data of the National Cooperative Council, the level of organisation of agricultural producers in farmers' cooperatives in other EU countries is much higher than in Poland. For example, in the Netherlands, Ireland, France or Germany, it is respectively 98%, 90%, 80% and 70%, while in Poland it is about 15%.⁷⁴

On 1 December 2018, the Act of 4 October 2018 on Farmers' Cooperatives came into force.⁷⁵ This law regulates issues related to strengthening the role of cooperatives in agriculture. It responds to the needs and expectations of farmers for support in associating in cooperatives and their functioning in such entities. It follows from the justification of the Act that the existing forms of agricultural cooperatives are inadequate, as they only cover a selected, rather narrow range of activities limited, in principle, to carrying out classic agricultural activities. However, the new provisions have not repealed the provisions on agricultural production cooperatives and cooperatives of agricultural associations, but refer to the joint cooperation of farmers especially with regard to products produced on the farms. All in all, they provide an incentive to strengthen cooperation in the agricultural sector, with the ultimate aim of strengthening the economic and bargaining position of agricultural producers.

A farmers' cooperative carries out its activities on the basis of the Law on Farmers' Cooperatives and its registered statute. In matters not regulated by the Act, the provisions of the Cooperative Law are applied. A farmers' cooperative is a voluntary association of natural or legal persons:

- 1) who run a farm within the meaning of the provisions on agricultural tax or who carry out agricultural activities within the scope of special divisions of agricultural production, who are producers of agricultural products or groups of such producers, or who breed or rear fish (farmers);

⁷³ Act of 16 September 1982 – Cooperative Law (uniform text: Journal of Laws 2021, item 648).

⁷⁴ See Ocena Skutków Regulacji do projektu ustawy o spółdzielniach rolników [Assessment of the Impact of Regulations for the draft act on farmers' cooperatives] (print no. 1425, 8th Term).

⁷⁵ Journal of Laws, item 2073.

- 2) who are non-farmers carrying out storage, warehousing, sorting, packaging or processing of agricultural products or groups of such products, or fish, produced by the farmers referred to in point (1), or agricultural support service activities involving the provision of services to the farmers referred to in point (1) using machinery, tools or equipment for the production of agricultural products or groups of such products or fish by those farmers (non-farmers);
- 3) with variable membership and a variable share fund, which carries out joint economic activities in the interests of its members.

The scope of activity of a farmers' cooperative is to carry out economic activities for the benefit of its members in the field of:

- 1) planning the farmers' production of products or groups of products and adapting it to market conditions;
- 2) concentrating supply and organising the sale of products or groups of products produced by farmers;
- 3) concentrating demand and organising the acquisition of the necessary means of production of products or groups of products for farmers.

In addition to the above-mentioned activities, a farmers' cooperative may carry out other economic activities such as storage, packaging, standardisation, processing of products, provision of services to farmers with the production of products, sale of products, or dissemination of environmentally beneficial cultivation methods, production technologies or waste management methods to its members. A farmers' cooperative may also carry out, for the benefit of its members, service activities other than the provision of services connected with the production of products by farmers, as well as social, educational and cultural activities, with the reservation that the income from the conduct of these activities may not in total exceed 25% of the cooperative's income obtained in a given financial year.

The founders of a farmers' cooperative may be farmers, the number of which may not be less than 10. A farmers' cooperative must have at least 10 members who are farmers, unless the statutes require a higher number. Importantly, a farmers' cooperative may not refuse to admit a farmer or a non-farmer as a member if he or she meets the requirement set out in the Act and the statute. Farmers' cooperatives may also associate in unions of farmers' cooperatives.

In order to encourage the establishment of farmers' cooperatives, the legislator has provided for exemptions from inheritance and donation tax, real estate tax and corporate income tax. *Inter alia*, the acquisition of rights to a share in a farmers' cooperative was exempted from inheritance and donation tax, and buildings and structures or parts thereof and the land occupied under them which are the property of, or held in perpetual usufruct by farmers' cooperatives were exempted from real estate tax. As regards corporate income tax, the income of a farmers' cooperative, conducting its activity as a micro-enterprise, from the sale of agricultural products or groups of such products was exempted from tax. It must be emphasised that the above exemptions constitute state aid within the meaning of Article 107 of the TFEU.

2.3

Changes in agricultural retail trade (ART)

In Poland, agricultural retail trade (ART) is a form of activity related to the production and direct sale of food (including processed food) by farmers. It was introduced into the Polish legal order by the Act of 16 November 2016 amending certain acts to facilitate the sale of food by farmers,⁷⁶ which came into force on 1 January 2017. The basic condition for conducting ART is that the produced and marketed food must come wholly or partly from own cultivation, breeding or rearing. The first regulation of ART provided for the production and processing of food on a smaller scale and its sale to final consumers (throughout the country) and to local establishments conducting retail trade for the final consumer (in a limited area – the voivodeship in which the production of food within the framework of ART takes place and the counties or cities constituting the seat of the voivode or the voivodeship assembly, adjacent to this voivodeship). The amount of revenue exempted from income tax on the sale of plant and animal products processed in a manner other than industrially within the framework of ART, with the exception of processed plant and animal products obtained within the framework of conducted special divisions of agricultural production and products subject to excise tax under separate regulations exempted from income tax, was PLN 40,000. Once the amount of PLN 40,000 was exceeded, a farmer conducting ART could choose to tax income above that amount with a lump-sum income tax of 2%. In order to benefit from the lump sum, he or she should submit a written declaration on the choice of lump-sum taxation on registered income for a given tax year.

When the ART legislation was in force from 2017, the following problems emerged. First, it was not possible to supply food produced by farmers to retail establishments for the final consumer (e.g. shops, restaurants, canteens) throughout the country. Second, there were maximum limits on food sold within the framework of ART also to final consumers. Third, the then-applicable income tax-free income amount of PLN 40 000 limited ART in practice. A farmer, after exceeding the amount of PLN 40 000, was obliged to make tax settlements and pay income tax. However, in order to need to avoid paying tax, farmers limited their ART activities to the tax exemption amount. Income from the sale of products within the framework of ART, after exceeding the threshold of PLN 40 000 was reported in the tax returns: for 2017 – by 106 taxpayers, for 2018 – by 122 taxpayers and for 2019 – by 153 taxpayers.⁷⁷

By the Act of 15 December 2021 amending certain acts to facilitate agricultural retail trade by farmers,⁷⁸ the provisions on ART were amended. The definition of ART was amended by clarifying the origin of ingredients used in food production. Single-ingredient food should come entirely from the farmer's own cultivation, breeding or rearing, while food with more than one ingredient (e.g. meat products, dairy products, bread, ready-made meals) should contain at least one ingredient coming entirely from the farmer's own cultivation, breeding or rearing.

There was also an extension of the area in which deliveries of food produced within the framework of ART to establishments retailing for the final consumer in the entire area of Poland – the same as directly for the final consumer. In addition, the maximum limits of food sold within ART to final con-

⁷⁶ Journal of Laws, item 1961.

⁷⁷ Ocena Skutków Regulacji ustawy o zmianie niektórych ustaw w celu ułatwienia prowadzenia przez rolników handlu detalicznego [Assessment of the impact of the Act on amending certain laws to facilitate retail trade by farmers].

⁷⁸ Journal of Laws 2022, item 138.

sumers were abolished, but they remained for establishments retailing for the final consumer. According to the legislator's assumptions, the changes should lead to an increase in the area of supply, as well as an increase in the market for food sold within ART.

However, the loosening of administrative restrictions on ART would not have affected the development of this form of activity if the tax law had not been amended. This coherence was noticed by the legislator itself, which resulted in an increase in the amount of income exempt from income tax from PLN 40,000 to PLN 100,000. The amending law entered into force retroactively in this part on 1 January 2022. The amendment in the remaining part came into force on 4 February 2022.

3. Rural areas

3.1

Various preparations are underway in Poland to implement some of the principles of "A long-term Vision for the EU's Rural Areas - Towards stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous rural areas by 2040." The Commission's communication is not a legal act and does not have direct legal effects in Polish law. According to the Polish government, the Commission's communication is positively evaluated. According to the Polish government, the main challenges have been correctly identified by the European Commission and coincide with the vision of rural areas indicated in the Strategy for Sustainable Rural, Agricultural and Rural Development adopted in October 2019. Strategy for the Sustainable Development of Rural Areas, Agriculture and Fisheries 2030. The strategy is Poland's idea of rural development.

The measures taken, for example, aim to change the land management system. To this end, a comprehensive amendment to the Law on Planning and Spatial Development was introduced in 2023, which, for example, specifies the location of large photovoltaic farms, or wind farms. This will allow faster development of rural areas, as well as more climate-friendly energy. The introduction of mandatory general plans will also speed up investment processes, while preserving public participation in land use decision-making.

At the same time, individual legislative actions are implemented not only through this Commission communication, but primarily through current policy needs. Therefore, it is difficult to unequivocally assess to what extent the Polish legislator is really guided by the Commission's communication in its actions, and to what extent it pursues its own political goals. It is true that in the justifications to drafts of Polish legislation there are mentions of the Commission's communication and that these acts implement certain goals from the communication, but this should be considered more in the postulatory version than actual legal solutions.

3.2

In terms of labor regulations, the labor law was amended in 2023 and introduced the possibility of remote work. At the outset, however, it should be noted that remote work in Polish agriculture has so far been quite underutilized. The changes introduced regulate the principles of remote work, but are unlikely to increase its role in agriculture, where direct work in the field, on the farm, with animals or processing is required. In the Polish Labor Code, remote work is considered, according to Article 6718, to be work that can be performed wholly or partially at a place designated by the employee and agreed with the employer on a case-by-case basis, including at the employee's home address, in particular

using means of direct communication at a distance. The Labor Code introduces three types of remote work: total remote work - work performed exclusively remotely (100% of working time remotely); partial remote work, so-called hybrid - work performed partly at the workplace and partly in the form of remote work; occasional remote work - performed each time at the request of the employee submitted in writing or electronically, for a maximum of 24 days per calendar year.

At the same time, such remote work is subject to a number of conditions. Remote work may be performed at the direction of the employer: during a state of emergency, a state of epidemic emergency or a state of epidemic emergency, and for a period of 3 months after their cancellation, or during a period in which it is temporarily impossible for the employer to provide safe and hygienic working conditions at the employee's current place of work due to force majeure - if the employee submits immediately before the order is issued a statement in paper or electronic form that he has the premises and technical conditions to perform remote work. In this regard, special conditions have been introduced for parents (especially women) of young children to facilitate the performance of remote work. According to the Polish Labor Code, the employer is obliged to grant the request of an employee of a pregnant employee, an employee raising a child up to the age of 4, as well as an employee taking care of another member of the immediate family or another person remaining in a common household, who has a disability certificate or a certificate with a significant degree of disability, to perform remote work, unless it is not possible due to the organization of work or the type of work performed by the employee.

The rules for performing remote work shall be specified in an agreement between the employer and the company trade union organization, and in the case where more than one company trade union organization operates at the employer - in an agreement between the employer and these organizations. If there are no company trade union organizations at a given employer, the employer shall determine the rules for remote work in the regulations after consultation with employee representatives selected in accordance with the procedure adopted at the employer. Polish labor legislation on remote work regulates in detail the obligations of the employer, the employee, as well as the incurring of costs by the various entities involved in the implementation of remote work and the control of the performance of remote work.

In terms of the many facilitations for women, organizations, conducting non-agricultural activities implementing the principles of the Common Agricultural Policy are indicated in the Polish National Strategic Plan where facilitations were introduced for groups of agricultural producers, or for women at least in the young farmer program. A farmer can start a business. However, it should be borne in mind that such an event has tax consequences in terms of PIT, VAT and property tax. According to the Law on Social Insurance for Farmers, which has been amended many times recently, Article 5a indicates that a farmer or a household member who, having been subject to full insurance by virtue of the law for at least 3 years continuously, begins to conduct non-agricultural business activity or begins to cooperate in the conduct of such activity, is still subject to this insurance during the period of conducting non-agricultural business activity or cooperation in the conduct of such activity, if he simultaneously meets the following conditions: he submits a statement to the Fund on the continuation of this insurance within 14 days from the date of commencement of non-agricultural business activity or cooperation in carrying out this activity; at the same time, he continues to carry out agricultural activity or permanently works in an agricultural farm, covering an area of agricultural land exceeding 1 hectare of calculation area, or in a special section; he is not an employee and is not in a service relationship; he does not have an established right to a pension or to social security benefits; the amount of income

tax due for the previous tax year on income from non-agricultural business activity does not exceed the amount of PLN 4088. According to Article 5a paragraph 2, the following are also considered as commencement of non-agricultural business activity: resumption of non-agricultural business activity, the conduct of which has been periodically suspended; a change in the type or subject of the activity performed according to the Polish Classification of Activities (PKD).

4. European Green Deal

The European Green Deal adopted on 11 December 2019⁷⁹ envisages a profound and holistic transformation geared towards achieving climate goals through a circular economy, elimination of pollution, more sustainable use of natural resources, especially soils and water. It is a new strategy for growth that aims to transform the EU into a fair and prosperous society living in a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy that achieves zero net greenhouse gas emissions in 2050 and where economic growth is decoupled from the use of natural resources. It also aims to protect, preserve and enhance the EU's natural capital. The transition to a zero-carbon economy must involve all areas of the economy, not only energy, transport or industry, but also agriculture. Implementing the Green Deal requires the formulation of specific EU strategies and policies relating to biodiversity (**Biodiversity Strategy**⁸⁰), forest protection (Forestry Strategy⁸¹) but also agricultural policy. The key strategic documents relating to agriculture are the agricultural strategy (**Farm to Fork Strategy**⁸²) announced in May 2020. These three strategies are complemented by the first EU strategy relating to soil protection (EU Soil Strategy⁸³). These strategic acts formulate the challenges and objectives for a fair, healthy, environmentally friendly European food system, described as very ambitious. These include the promotion of more extensive farming practices, such as grazing and mowing, compatible with the biodiversity of agricultural land.

In addition, in 2021 The European Commission has proposed a package of new and updated legislation called "**Fit for 55**" consisting of 13 interconnected and updated rules and 6 new climate and energy legal solutions, among which are the strengthening of the rules for enhancing carbon sequestration in the land use and forestry sector (LULUCF -Land use, land use change and forestry)⁸⁴, regulated from 2018 regulation (EU) 2018/841 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 on the inclusion of greenhouse gas emissions and removals from land use, land use change and forestry activities in the 2030 climate and energy policy framework⁸⁵. The preamble of the act (recital 12) highlights the LULUCF sector, including agricultural land, has a direct and significant impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services. Therefore, support for actions in this sector related to both mitigation and adaptation to climate change must be implemented and coherence with CAP instruments must be

⁷⁹ Communication from the Commission European Green Deal, Brussels, 11.12.2019, COM(2019) 640 final.

⁸⁰ Communication from the Commission Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 Bringing nature back into our lives, COM/2020/380 final.

⁸¹ Communication from the Commission Forest Strategy for 2030, COM/2021/572 final.

⁸² Communication from the Commission of 20 May 2020 Farm to Fork Strategy. For a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system Brussels, 20.5.2020, COM(2020) 381 final.

⁸³ Commission Communication of 17 November 2021 EU Soil Strategy 2030. Reaping the benefits of healthy soil for people, food, nature and climate'.

⁸⁴ In March 2023. Parliament approved legislation governing the land use, land use change and forestry (LULUCF) sector, which increases the sector's carbon sequestration in the EU by 15% by 2030.

⁸⁵ Official Journal of the EU L 156 of 19.6.2018, p. 1.

ensured. All sectors must make an appropriate contribution in terms of reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

On 14 July 2023, Polish Government⁸⁶ challenged the compatibility of the proposed Fit for 55 package of the Regulation of 10 May 2023, of the European Parliament and of the EU Council 2023/956 establishing a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)⁸⁷ and amendments to Regulation 2018/841 by filing **a complaint with the CJEU** against the proposed amendments, indicating, inter alia, that the LULUCF Regulation was adopted on the wrong legal basis, additionally violating the competence of Member States by interfering in the way forest management is carried out, despite the lack of EU competence in this area. On 17 July 2023, it was reported that a further 3 complaints had been lodged with the CJEU on the compatibility of the proposed changes under the Fit for 55 package.

For this reason, an important policy objective is also to ensure coherence with the objectives of the EU **Biodiversity Strategy**. On arable land, the introduction of landscape elements rich in biodiversity (so-called 'ecosystem islands') such as flower strips, hedgerows, trees, fallow land, small ponds, etc. is required. The most serious changes concern the reduction of the use of fertilisers and pesticides. The new agricultural policy also envisages: a shift to agro-ecological practices such as organic production or agro-forestry; the removal of invasive plants; the reintroduction of extensive agriculture; the restoration of grasslands; and the re-wetting of agriculturally used peatlands. On 5 July 2023, The European Commission presented Communication "**Ensuring a resilient and sustainable use of the EU's natural resources**"⁸⁸ highlighted the importance of soils and the need to protect them. The document assumes the creation of a framework for monitoring the condition of all soils across the EU⁸⁹ and envisages an improvement in their condition in the Union by 2050. It is worth stressing that the document recognises that the actions taken within the framework of the strategy are based on practices already supported for several years by the CAP and, apart from these, no new obligations for farmers are introduced.

The condition of Poland's soils is described as average, 70% of Poland's soils are formed mainly from post-glacial clays and sands, which have been heavily washed and sorted by glacial waters. In addition, more than 28% of arable land soils have formed from loose and weakly loamy sands and gravels⁹⁰. In Poland, there is also the phenomenon of salinisation and acidification of soils occurring for both natural and anthropogenic reasons⁹¹. As a result, it is estimated that 40% of Polish soils are characterised by poor quality and agricultural suitability⁹².

⁸⁶ <https://www.gov.pl/web/klimat/polska-zaskarzyla-do-tsue-kolejne-dwa-akty-prawne-bedace-czescia-paki-etu-fit-for-55>

⁸⁷ OJ L 130, 16.5.2023, p. 52.

⁸⁸ Commission Communication of 5 July 2023. Ensuring a resilient and sustainable use of the EU's natural resources, COM(2023) 410 final.

⁸⁹ Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Soil Monitoring and Resilience, COM(2023) 416 final.

⁹⁰ S. Krasowicz, W. Oleszek, J. Horabik, R. Dębicki, J. Jankowiak, T. Stuczyński, J. Jadczyński, Rational management of the soil environment of Poland. "Polish Journal of Agronomy" 2011, no. 7, p. 43-58.

⁹¹ A. Placek, M. Kacprzak, K. Fijałkowski, Soil salinisation in Poland, causes and remediation [in:] G. Malina (ed.), Remediation, reclamation and revitalisation, Poznań 2014, pp.97-114.

⁹² T. Witek, Wpływ jakości gleb na plonowanie roślin uprawnych, "Zeszyty Problemowe Postępu Nauk Rolniczych" 1979, no. 224, p. 35-47, as well as S. Lekan, H. Terelak, "Zróżnicowanie środowiska glebowo-rolniczego Polski, Materiały konferencji naukowej nt. "Ochrona i wykorzystanie rolniczej przestrzeni produkcyjnej Polski", IUNG Puławy 1997, session I and II, pp. 7-21.

Polish legal regulations relating to soil protection were comprehensively modernised in 2014 as a result of the transposition of the provisions of Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control)⁹³, especially with regard to the ordering of the system of legal protection of the land surface or remediation⁹⁴. The **monitoring of soil quality takes** place in Poland in two ways. The assessment of the condition of soils is part of the subject matter scope of the State Environmental Monitoring (art. 23 sec. 11 item 3 of the Act on the Inspection of Environmental Protection⁹⁵), which is carried out in a cyclic manner, using standardised methods of collecting, gathering and processing data. In addition, pursuant to Art. 18 (1) and (19) of the Act of 3 February 1995 on the protection of agricultural and forest land⁹⁶ on land located in the areas of limited use, existing around industrial plants, but also devastated and degraded land located outside the areas of limited use, the starost ensures that periodic examinations of the level of contamination of soils and plants are carried out every 3 years. If the periodic examinations show that the crops obtained are not suitable for consumption or processing, the costs of the examinations shall be charged to the industrial plant, and the contaminated land shall be excluded from production in accordance with the procedure set out in Art. 11 par. 1 u.g.r. The consequences of these decisions shall be borne by the industrial plant responsible for the contamination.

In the Polish legal system, the protection of the earth's surface, including soils, is the subject of legal protection in the Environmental Protection Law⁹⁷, in which the scope of protection of this natural resource is indicated in Art. 101 p.o.ś. **Protection of the earth surface (soils)** consists in: 1) rational management; 2) preservation of environmental, economic, social and cultural functions (including but not limited to: food and biomass production, storage, filtration and transformation of nutrients, substances and water, basis for the development of life and biodiversity, source of raw materials, carbon reservoir, collection of geological, geomorphological and archaeological heritage); 3) prevention of pollution by risk-causing substances and remediation; 4) preservation of the best possible soil condition by preventing: water and wind erosion, a decrease in soil humus content, compaction, by which is meant an increase in bulk density and a decrease in soil porosity, salinisation due to the accumulation of soluble salts in the soil, and acidification activities; 5) minimising the degree and mitigating the effects of soil sealing by limiting the area of soil covered by development to the necessary minimum and preserving or creating biologically active areas of soil capable of mitigating the degrading effects of developed areas and environmental pollution; 6) preventing earth mass movements and their effects; and 7) counteracting adverse changes to the natural relief of the earth's surface. In view of the function performed, the level of permissible content of risk-causing substances in soil or ground Art. 101a p.o.ś. has also been differentiated.

⁹³ OJ L 334, 17.12.2010, p. 17.

⁹⁴ More extensively on this topic M. Górski, Protection of the Earth's surface in the provisions of the amendments to the Environmental Protection Law and other laws of February 2014. [in:] G. Malina (ed.), Remediation, reclamation and revitalisation, Poznań 2014, pp. 61-77.

⁹⁵ Act of 20 July 1991 on the Environmental Protection Inspection, i.e. Journal of Laws 2023, item 824.

⁹⁶ Act of 3 February 1995 on the protection of agricultural and forest land, i.e. Dz. U. from 2022, item 2409, hereinafter cited as: "u.g.r."

⁹⁷ Act of 27 April 2001. Environmental Protection Law, i.e. Dz. U. of 2022, item 2556 as amended, hereinafter cited as "p.o.ś."

Due to the productive functions of the land surface (soils), the first solutions for the **protection of agricultural land** were established already in the 1960s, and the Act in force is the third legal act in this respect⁹⁸. The legal protection of agricultural and forest land in the Polish legislation was conceived as a separate holistic protection, uniform for the whole country and functional, and, as the evolution of normative solutions shows, it was not directly subordinated to the legal regulations of environmental protection⁹⁹. The Polish regulation, however, lacks instruments of regionalisation of impact in the field of soil protection.

In the current legal status, two basic directions of land protection can be distinguished: **quantitative protection** (the first group of tasks - protection consisting in limiting the designation of agricultural and forest land for other purposes, inter alia, through the necessity to obtain consent for change of designation of agricultural and forest land and decisions to exclude land from agricultural and forest production) and **qualitative protection** (the remaining group of tasks - protection of soil productivity, inter alia, through prevention of soil erosion or restoration of the value of degraded agricultural and forest land through the obligation to reclaim the land). In terms of quantitative protection of land, the legislator granted the public administration bodies the power to issue permits for the use of agricultural and forest land for non-agricultural and non-forest purposes, having the form of administrative decisions. In the light of Art. 7(1) of the Act, the designation of agricultural and forest land for non-agricultural and non-forest purposes is made on the basis of a spatial development plan drawn up by the municipal authorities in accordance with the provisions of the Act on Planning and Spatial Development. In recent years, there has been a significant liberalisation of the provisions on quantitative protection of agricultural land by adding exemptions to the obligation to obtain consent for non-agricultural and non-forest use of agricultural land constituting agricultural land of the highest quality classes I-III, upon fulfilment of several conditions altogether. The exemption also covers areas for which a local spatial development plan is not drawn up. Pursuant to Art. 10a u.g.r., restrictions on the use of land for non-agricultural purposes do not apply to agricultural land located within the administrative boundaries of cities. Qualitative protection instruments may include the obligation imposed on owners of land constituting agricultural land and land rehabilitated for agricultural purposes in Art. 15(1) u.g.r. who are obliged to prevent soil degradation, including in particular erosion and earth mass movements. Much broader requirements in this respect have been introduced in terms of **cross-compliance requirements for good agricultural and environmental condition**¹⁰⁰ inter alia in terms of minimum soil cover, where an area of at least 30% of arable land, located in areas at risk of water erosion, which is part of the agricultural holding, shall be left under soil cover from at least 1 November to 15 February. Minimum land management conditions have also been introduced for arable land located on slopes of more than 20°, reflecting the conditions of the land in order to reduce erosion. The requirements set out in the Soil Strategy have been implemented through the **conditionality requirement** in the Law of 8 February 2023 on the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027¹⁰¹,

⁹⁸ The first was the Act of 26.10.1971 on the protection of agricultural and forest land and land reclamation, Journal of Laws No. 249 as amended.

⁹⁹ For more on the views of the doctrine of agricultural and environmental law, see M.A. Król, A. Kaźmierska-Patrzyzna, *Gospodarowanie zasobami geosfery* [in:] M. Górski (ed.), *Prawo ochrony środowiska*, Warsaw 2021, pp. 602-604.

¹⁰⁰ Ordinance of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 9 March 2015 on standards for good agricultural culture compatible with environmental protection, Journal of Laws. 2015, item 344.

¹⁰¹ Now a change resulting from the Act of 8 February 2023 on the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027, Journal of Laws, item 412 and the acts implementing the Act.

including in particular Art. 56 of the Law establishing GAEC 1 and GAEC 9, or Art. 169(4) establishing GAEC 2 and the standards contained in the implementing acts of the Law¹⁰².

Inland wetlands, including bogs¹⁰³, also play an important role in shaping the **biodiversity of extensive agricultural land**. For this reason, the protection of wetlands, peatlands, is also an important element of the New Green Deal and complementary strategies. These extremely valuable natural resources in Poland have for decades been subject to economic appropriation due to predatory management, especially drainage irrigation for agriculture and extraction of peat as a mineral. Nowadays, they are protected under international agreements, especially the Ramsar Convention¹⁰⁴, by listing the areas on the so-called "Red List of Wetlands" and subjecting them to protection under national regulations, inter alia by including them in forms of nature protection.

In Poland, the poor state of wetlands is highlighted, inter alia, in the strategic document "National Ecological Policy 2030 - Strategy for development in the field of environment and water management", adopted by the Council of Ministers on 16 July 2019¹⁰⁵ where the poor state of preservation of peatlands and degradation of low peatlands is indicated. Poland has few Ramsar-listed areas compared to other EU countries or Ukraine, the Polish Strategy for Wetlands in Poland with an Action Plan for 2006-2013 created a list of 43 areas, but there are still only 19 protected nature areas, with a total area of 153,000 ha, listed under the Convention in 2023, with the last three listed in 2017. We have also not had a strategy for the protection of wetlands in Poland, as required by the Convention, for ten years.

The legal regulation of the protection of peat bogs is mainly found in the Law of 2004 on nature protection¹⁰⁶ by including deserving of protection remnants of ecosystems of importance for the preservation of biodiversity, including natural water reservoirs, mid-field and mid-forest ponds, swamps and peat bogs in the legal form of nature protection defined as ecological uses normalized in Art. 42 u.o.p. **Peat bogs and ponds** constitute agricultural land (Art. 2 (1) (9) u.g.r.) and, as agricultural land, are **subject to qualitative protection** consisting in preventing the processes of degradation and devastation of agricultural land and damage to agricultural production caused by non-agricultural activities and earth mass movements. Qualitative protection also includes measures to promote reclamation understood as the improvement of physical and chemical properties of soil, regulation of water relations, restoration of soils, strengthening of slopes and construction of necessary roads. Land protection includes activities aimed at preserving peat bogs and ponds as natural water reservoirs (Art. 3(1)(4) of the Law on Land), as well as limiting changes in the natural relief of the land surface. The

¹⁰² GAEC 3 - GAEC 9 standards in the regulations Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 10 March 2023 on standards and detailed conditions for their application, Journal of Laws, item 478 and SMR 1 - SMR 11 standards. Announcement of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development on the list of basic requirements taking into account national regulations implementing European Union regulations, M.P. 2020, item 341.

¹⁰³ H. Piórkowski, W. Dembek (eds.), The role of wetlands in the environment, GIS https://www.itp.edu.pl/GIS_mokradla/html/index.php?page=zagrozenia (accessed 12 July 2023).

¹⁰⁴ Ramsar Convention on Wetlands, signed 1971 in Ramsar, Iran, ratified Dz. U. 1978 no. 7 item 24.

¹⁰⁵ M.P. 2019 item 794, pp. 217, 221, 226-227. According to Appendix 1 to the State Environmental Policy 2030 Diagnoses in individual areas of the State Environmental Policy 2030, terrestrial hydrogenic habitats in Poland cover 4 340 000 hectares, or 13.9% of the country's area. Approximately ¼ of these are peat bogs, while the remainder are wetlands on mineral substrates associated with river floodplains. Inland open waters, comprising reservoirs and watercourses (rivers, lakes, estuaries, ponds and dam reservoirs), cover about 3% of the country's area. Peatlands, in the sense of living peat-forming ecosystems, cover about 202,000 ha (0.6% of the country's area). The total length of watercourses is about 98,000 km.

¹⁰⁶ Act of 16 April 2004 on nature protection, i.e. Dz. U. of 2023, item 1336, hereinafter cited as: "u.o.p."

legal issue of peatland protection in Poland is multifaceted and regulation is scattered. Protective provisions can be found in the Forest Act¹⁰⁷ and the provisions of the Act of 20 July 2018. Water Law¹⁰⁸. Peat bogs are also a mineral and are regulated in terms of the conditions of mineral exploitation under the Act of 9 June 2011. Geological and Mining Law¹⁰⁹. Wetlands are still not sufficiently protected and no new instruments have been established.

In Poland, **water resources originate in rural and forest areas**, which cover more than 90% of the country. Agricultural activity has a negative effect on the condition of surface waters, including in our region of Europe the marine waters of the Baltic Sea through the occurrence of nitrogen and phosphorus compounds, and causes a dangerous **eutrophication** phenomenon for living water resources¹¹⁰. Legal regulation in this area was introduced in the 1990s through the provisions of Council Directive 91/676/EEC of 12 December 1991 concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources¹¹¹ aims to reduce and prevent further pollution. Member States are obliged to develop and promote codes of good agricultural practice setting out how to ensure protection against nitrate pollution of all waters. They are also obliged to identify areas at risk of nitrate pollution. Action programmes in this regard must be implemented by imposing and enforcing appropriate restrictions on agricultural activities.

A specific type of sustainable water and wastewater management is the obligation to take specific measures to **reduce and prevent eutrophication of** inland surface waters, internal sea waters and coastal waters. In the Polish legal system, these issues were regulated by the provisions of the Water Law of 18 July 2001¹¹², and after the introduction of the Water Framework Directive¹¹³ of the Water Law Act of 2017, where this issue was standardised in Chapter 4, Section I. *Protection of waters against nitrates from agricultural sources* (Art. 102 - 112 p.w.). Compared to Art. 47 d.p.w., the new provisions represent a significant expansion of the regulation, at least in quantitative terms. However, a number of new provisions of a substantive nature should be noted. The importance of this issue was accentuated by the legislator himself by introducing the date of entry into force of the provisions of Chapter 4 on the day following the date of promulgation. These provisions entered into force on 24 August 2017, without the application of a four-month *vacatio legis*, as in the case of the substantive provisions of the Act. According to the provision of Art. 102(1) p.w., agricultural production (this term is not defined, but its conceptual scope has been made more precise by the inclusion of special departments of agricultural production and activities where animal excrement is stored or fertilisers applied) should be carried out in such a way as to prevent pollution of water by nitrates from agricultural sources. This provision, essentially unchanged, replicates Art. 47(1) of the d.p.w.

¹⁰⁷ Protection implemented on the basis of Article 13(1)(1) of the Act of 28.09.1991 on forests, i.e. Dz. U. from 2023 item 1356. This provision obliges forest owners to, inter alia, "preserve natural swamps and bogs in forests".

¹⁰⁸ i.e. Dz. U. 2022, as amended. The objectives for protected areas that include peatlands include, inter alia, the preservation or restoration of the proper water conditions of these peatlands.

¹⁰⁹ Dz. U. from 2023, item 633.

¹¹⁰ M.A. Król, *Gospodarowanie zasobów wodnymi na obszarach wiejskich a prawna ochrona morza Bałtyckiego przed eurofizacją* [in:] D. Łobos-Kotowska, P. Gała, M. Stańko, *Współczesne problemy prawa rolnego i cywilnego*. Professor Teresa Kurowska's jubilee book, Warsaw 2018, pp. 213-235.

¹¹¹ OJ EU L 375, p. 1, hereinafter: Nitrates Directive.

¹¹² i.e. Dz. U. from 2017, item 1121, Act repealed as of 1 January 2018, hereinafter cited as: "d.p.w."

¹¹³ Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy, OJ L 327, 22.12.2000, p. 1-73, hereinafter cited as: "Water Framework Directive".

In the Polish legal system, we have three main instruments to protect waters against eutrophication: (1) agricultural use of sewage sludge; (2) protection of waters from nitrates of agricultural origin; (3) legal instruments against water pollution as a result of excessive chemicalisation in agriculture.

Agricultural use of wastewater is regulated by Art. 84 p.w., which establishes a general rule limiting the discharge of wastewater into water and land. A derogation is laid down for the agricultural use of wastewater to irrigate agricultural land, including by adding materials to the soil or irrigating and fertilising ponds used for rearing or breeding fish. The legislator in Art. 84(4) p.w. imposes an absolute prohibition on the agricultural use of wastewater applies when the ground is frozen or covered with snow; when the water table is shallower than 1.5 m from the ground surface or from the bottom of a drainage ditch; in areas with a slope of more than 10% for arable land and 20% for meadows, pastures and forest tree plantations; and in areas of special flood risk during a forecasted water surge. The susceptibility to eutrophication of waters will be the basis for the use of pollutants in amounts higher than the maximum pollutant limits when setting the conditions for the discharge of waste water in the water permit to be issued.

The legislator has established four instruments for **qualitative water protection against nitrate run-off from agricultural sources**: 1) designation of surface and groundwater and areas particularly vulnerable to pollution by nitrates from agricultural sources (OSN areas); 2) an action programme aimed at reducing nitrogen run-off from agricultural sources (OSN action programme – Art. 104 p.w.), 3) sets of recommendations for good agricultural practice; 4) a nitrogen fertilisation plan.

The most important instrument for counteracting eutrophication is the establishment of **areas particularly vulnerable to pollution by nitrates from agricultural sources**. In the previous legal status (2001 Act), these areas were designated by the competent public administration bodies, taking into account, inter alia, the degree of eutrophication of inland surface waters, internal sea waters and coastal waters for which nitrogen was a factor of eutrophication. For these areas, a set of principles of good agricultural practice is being developed by the minister responsible for agriculture. In these areas, nitrogen run-off from agricultural sources into waters had to be reduced. For this purpose, a remediation programme was also developed within the meaning of Art. 84 p.o.ś., and the degree of eutrophication of inland surface waters was assessed every 4 years. Poland, despite the fact that waters from 99.7% of our country flow into the Baltic Sea, recognised only **4.5% of the territory** as vulnerable to nitrate pollution, while already in 2012 in Austria, Denmark, Finland, the Netherlands, Ireland, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Germany, Slovenia, the Flanders region and Northern Ireland the area of the country covered by OSN was 100%¹¹⁴. The fundamental change in the new water protection legislation is on the **recognition of the entire national territory as an OSN area**. For the designated OSN area, covering the whole country, on the basis of Article 104.1 p.w., one programme of measures is developed (instead of nine hitherto), which, however, will be differentiated depending on soil, climatic, water and environmental conditions, relief, land management, including the system of crop rotation (Art. 104 (3)(4) p.w.), which is justified due to the necessity of regionalisation of impact. The provision also allows for the possibility of differentiating measures and treatments according to the number of animals kept, the size of the farmland or the intensity of agricultural production. This already makes it possible to apply derogations for small farms with a low intensity of production.

¹¹⁴ Data based on Report from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament on the implementation of Council Directive 91/676/EEC concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources based on Member State reports for the period 2008-2011, COM/2013/0683 final.

For the designated OSN area (the area of the whole Poland), on the basis of Art. 104(1) p.w., one **action programme** is developed (instead of the existing nine), which, however, will be differentiated depending on soil, climatic, water and environmental conditions, landforms, land use, including the system of crop rotation (Art. 104(3)(4) p.w.), which is justified due to the necessity of regionalisation of the impact. Currently in force is the Ordinance of the Council of Ministers of 31 January 2023 on the "Programme of measures to reduce water pollution by nitrates from agricultural sources and to prevent further pollution"¹¹⁵. The most important measures indicated in the Action Programme include: setting conditions for the agricultural use of nitrogen fertilisers, e.g. near bodies of water, on areas with steep slopes, and on frozen, waterlogged or snow-covered soils; introducing periods during which the agricultural use of fertilisers is allowed; defining conditions for the storage of manure and the handling of leachate; defining a method for calculating the annual dose of manure containing no more than **170 kg N in pure component per hectare**. In contrast, however, there is no upper annual dose of fertiliser containing phosphorus (P). Programme from 2023 also set out rules for drawing up a nitrogen fertilisation plan.

An important instrument to implement the Green Deal is the requirement imposed on agricultural operators in the new Article 105a p.w. added to the Act in 2019.¹¹⁶ requirement to prepare a **nitrogen fertilisation plan** if: 1) the farm has more than 100 ha of agricultural land or they grow intensive crops on arable land of more than 50 ha or maintain a stocking density of more than 60 livestock units (DJP), 2) the poultry farm has more than 40,000 stands or the pig farm has more than 2,000 stands for pigs weighing more than 30 kg or 750 stands for sows, 3) farmers purchase manure from a non-EU importer.

The legal regulation of **organic farming** dates back to 2022 and is the Act of 23 June 2022 on organic farming and production¹¹⁷ transposing into the Polish legal order the Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council (EU) 2018/848 of 30 May 2018. on organic production and labelling of organic products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007¹¹⁸ and Regulation (EU) 2017/625 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2017 on official controls and other official acts performed to ensure the application of food and feed law and of rules on animal health and welfare, plant health and plant protection products¹¹⁹. Adopted in the form of an EU regulation, and therefore an act of general application throughout the Union, the legal solutions are intended to serve the implementation of the New Green Deal and specific strategies including, in particular, the Biodiversity Strategy and the Soil Strategy. The basic assumption is that organic production will be carried out on at least 25% of all EU agricultural land and that aquaculture will increase significantly.

This applies in particular to the assumption of reducing the use of pesticides, which is to be served by the ecoscheme "Organic farming" adopted within the Strategic Plan. This is regulated by the provisions of the Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 6 April 2023 on the detailed conditions and detailed procedure for granting and paying organic payments under the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027¹²⁰. The assumption is that this agriculture is to produce food using natural substances and processes, including a maximum reduction in chemical

¹¹⁵ Dz. U. from 2023, item 244.

¹¹⁶ Art. 105a added by Article 1(17) of the Act of 11 September 2019. (Dz.U. 2019, item 2170) amending the Act as of 23 November 2019.

¹¹⁷ Dz. U. from 2023, item 1235.

¹¹⁸ OJ EU L 150, 14.06.2018, p. 1.

¹¹⁹ OJ EU L 95, 07.04.2017, p. 1.

¹²⁰ Dz.U. from 2023 item 791.

methods of plant protection. A farmer implementing an organic commitment shall comply with the following requirements: (1) have an organic activity plan drawn up in the first year of the organic commitment; (2) keep an organic activity register for the agricultural land under organic commitment, listing: (a) the agro-technical operations carried out within the framework of the implemented package, in particular the application of fertilisers and the application of plant protection products, indicating the name and dose of the fertiliser and plant protection product used and the reason for the application of the plant protection product, and the mowing carried out, (b) the grazing of animals - if grazing is carried out - together with the date on which they were carried out; 3) comply with the relevant minimum requirements referred to in Art. 70(3)(b) of Regulation 2021/2115 concerning the use of fertilisers and plant protection products and other relevant mandatory requirements established by national law, as indicated in Annex 1 to the Regulation (withdrawal and precautionary periods for plant protection products, treatment records); 4) comply with the other requirements set out for individual packages in Annex 2 to the Regulation (inter alia, weed prevention and weed removal - maintenance of the soil as black fallow or sodding by regular mowing or application of other preventive measures against the spread of weeds).

In summary, it must be said that the changes proposed under the New Green Deal and the specific strategies have not been recognised in Poland and the level of implementation is not satisfactory. This is accompanied by a negative assessment of scientific circles¹²¹, which, on the basis of conducted analyses, concluded that as a result of the implementation of the assumptions of the New Green Deal there will be a decrease in the efficiency of crop production in Polish agriculture, agricultural production and farmers' income will decrease, it will be reflected in an increase in food prices, the international competitiveness of Polish agriculture will deteriorate, and it is not certain that all environmental objectives will be achieved. In addition, it was found that Polish agriculture is not prepared to fully implement the strategy and minimising the negative effects of the implementation of the New Green Deal³ will require financial and material support for agriculture from the state and the EU.

In Summer 2023 Poland has submitted a total of 4 complaints to the CJEU against the European Commission on the compliance of the proposed changes to the *Fit for 55* package with EU law. With regard to matters relating to agriculture, we have observed only positive changes in alignment with the assumptions of the new strategies resulting from the development of implementing acts for the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027.

5. CAP Strategic Plans and CAP 2023-2027

5.1

In accordance with the strategic declaration, the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027 (CAP) aims to support the sustainable development of Polish farms, the processing sector, and the improvement of living and working conditions in small rural communities. The CAP instruments are intended to support sustainable farming methods that are climate-friendly and environmentally protective, safeguarding water, soil, air, and biodiversity. They aim to encourage the production and

¹²¹ Wpływ Europejskiego Zielonego Ładu na polskie rolnictwo (Impact of the European Green Deal on Polish agriculture), Institute of Rural and Agricultural Development of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IRWiR PAN), Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation - National Research Institute (IUNG-PIB), Poznań University of Life Sciences (UPP), Warsaw 2021, pp. 15-19.

utilization of sustainable energy as well. The CAP also intends to enhance economic diversity, including the bioeconomy. The improvement of development dynamics is expected to increase the economic and social activity of rural inhabitants and marginalized individuals. The implementation of the Strategic Plan should incorporate the horizontal principle of equal opportunities and non-discrimination, including accessibility for people with disabilities, as well as equal treatment of women and men. Scientific achievements and innovative solutions, including digital ones, aimed at eliminating developmental barriers in rural areas and agriculture, are to be disseminated and implemented.

As part of the effort to reinforce the intelligent, competitive, resilient, and diverse agricultural sector that ensures long-term food security, a range of instruments has been designed to support the profitability and resilience of smaller farms, in addition to direct payments. This support includes investment aid and assistance in risk management and preventing African Swine Fever (ASF). It also encompasses support for supply chain organization, the development of small-scale processing, and participation in national and EU quality production systems. Investment support for processing and the introduction of products into circulation is also foreseen. The improvement of agrarian structure is an additional goal. Complementary support for supply chain organization, digitalization, and innovation in agriculture is planned to be realized through other national and EU programs.

Regarding environmental protection, including biodiversity conservation and climate action, and with the aim of contributing to the EU's environmental and climate objectives, including those stemming from the Paris Agreement, interventions have been designed to encourage farmers to adopt enhanced standards in agricultural production. These standards promote environmentally-friendly production methods, carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions reduction, soil quality improvement, and water retention enhancement. Investment support that considers water recycling and energy consumption reduction in production is also envisioned. The policy direction also seeks to increase forest cover, improve Poland's forest condition, and strengthen forest biodiversity. Training and advisory activities for farmers, as well as educational and informative initiatives for food consumers and local communities, are also planned. Support for environmental protection and climate change mitigation is also set to be implemented through other national and EU programs, including educational ones.

Within the framework of reinforcing the socio-economic structure of rural areas, it is recognized that the competitiveness of rural areas in Poland is dependent on improving technical infrastructure, enhancing access to essential services, and fostering entrepreneurship. The Strategic Plan includes interventions that encourage young individuals to engage in agricultural activities and support the creation and development of businesses in rural areas. Informative campaigns to encourage participation in operations supported by the EU are also planned. Information distribution channels will take into account the necessity of reaching disadvantaged groups.

In line with the regulations of the Polish Act of February 8, 2023, on the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023-2027 (Official Journal of the Republic of Poland from 2023, item 412; amendment: OJ from 2023, item 1530), direct payments are granted – in principle – to actively working farmers who engage in agricultural activities, provided that the total area of land covered by the region approved for basic income support in the possession of the farmer is not less than 1 hectare. Direct payments are granted based on the area of arable land or non-agricultural land units. The qualifying hectare for intervention in the form of direct payments constitutes the arable land of the given farm for which direct payments are applied and which is used for agricultural activities during the calendar year or is predominantly used for agricultural activities. Each reference parcel has a defined maximum

qualifying area within the agricultural land identification system. Direct payments in a given calendar year are granted for the area of qualifying land, not exceeding the maximum qualifying area.

Within the framework of the direct support system for 2023-2027 in Poland, eco-schemes have been introduced – a type of intervention in the form of direct payments, through which farmers can receive additional payments for implementing practices beneficial to the environment, climate, and animal welfare.

Payments under eco-schemes are granted to farmers in the form of payments for areas with honey-producing plants, payments for carbon and nutrient management in agriculture, payments for integrated plant production, payments for biological crop protection, payments for water retention in permanent grasslands, and animal welfare payments.

5.2

In the current programming period of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) in Poland, under the systems of direct support, basic income support unrelated to production is provided as an annual payment per qualifying hectare. This payment is uniform across the country and independent of the direction of agricultural production, as well as the achieved results and production size. Additionally, farmers are entitled to a redistributive payment if they own a total land area of at least 1 hectare and not exceeding 300 hectares. The redistributive payment applies to land owned by the farmer within the region approved for basic income support, up to a maximum of 30 hectares. Among the complementary payments unrelated to production, there is also a payment for young farmers. This payment is granted to a farmer who, in the first year of applying for this payment, is no more than 40 years old, manages a farm, meaning that they personally conduct agricultural activities within the farm, at their own expense and in their own name, bears costs, and reaps benefits associated with these activities, and possesses the appropriate vocational education or at least 3 years of work experience in agriculture.

Moreover, optional payments linked to animal and plant production are foreseen. In terms of animal production, these include payments for cows, cattle, sheep, and goats. For cow payments, female domestic cattle (*Bos taurus*) exceeding 24 months of age as of May 15, 2023, qualify. Cow payments are granted for a maximum of 20 animals. Cattle payments apply to male and female domestic cattle (*Bos taurus*) with an age not exceeding 24 months as of May 15, 2023, i.e., animals born no later than May 15, 2023. Cattle payments are granted for up to 20 animals. For sheep payments, a farmer who possesses at least 10 ewes (*Ovis aries*) that are at least 12 months old as of May 15, 2023, qualifies. There is no upper limit on the number of animals for this payment. For goat payments, a farmer who possesses at least 5 female domestic goats (*Capra hircus*) that are at least 12 months old as of May 15, 2023, qualifies. There is no upper limit on the number of animals for this payment.

Regarding plant production, the following payments are foreseen: payments for sugar beets, hops, flax, industrial hemp, tomatoes, strawberries, starch potatoes, fodder crops, and leguminous plants for seeds.

As part of the mechanism referred to as transitional national support, additional basic payments are also foreseen. These payments are granted for the cultivation of cereals, oilseed crops, high-protein crops, and arable land where sowing has taken place to improve soil fertility and mix or plow plant material, as well as for non-tobacco-related payments, which apply to tobacco production during the reference period.

As mentioned earlier, a new type of direct payment available to Polish farmers is payments under eco-schemes, for which 25% of the total financial allocation for direct payments has been set aside. Eco-schemes involve voluntary commitments by farmers to implement environmentally beneficial practices and animal welfare practices that exceed the requirements set within the conditionality mechanism.

Under the legal solutions adopted in 2023 in Poland, established after the deadline for submitting applications for direct payments, there is a possibility of granting small farm payments to farmers. This is based on a request submitted by the farmer if, in the application for payments for the year 2023, the total land area covered by the region approved for basic income support owned by the farmer is at least 1 hectare, and the area of these agricultural lands owned by the farmer as of May 31, 2023, was no more than 5 hectares. Small farm payments replace all other direct payments applied for in the application for payments for the year 2023 (basic income support, redistributive payment, young farmer payment, all payments related to production, and payments under eco-schemes). Farmers requesting small farm payments who applied for transitional national support (additional basic payment or non-tobacco-related payment) will also receive these payments. Regardless of the above, farmers will receive payments for less favored areas (LFA), ecological payments, agri-environment-climate payments, if they applied for these payments in an application submitted by July 25, 2023.

5.3

Within Pillar II of the CAP, interventions of an investment, cooperation and knowledge transfer, and digitalization nature are planned. This pillar also encompasses the provision of agri-environmental payments and payments for areas facing natural or specific constraints, known as LFA (Less Favored Areas).

Among the investment activities, support is envisaged for investments that improve the welfare of cattle and pigs, investments in agricultural holdings for renewable energy sources (RES) and energy efficiency improvements, investments preventing the spread of African Swine Fever (ASF), and investments contributing to environmental and climate protection. Support in the form of grants and other financial instruments for on-farm investments enhancing competitiveness is also planned, incorporating activities related to the modernization and restructuring of agricultural holdings, as well as premiums for young farmers.

Within agri-environmental and climate interventions, instruments are designed to protect valuable habitats and endangered species within Natura 2000 areas and beyond, promote organic farming, extensively manage meadows and pastures in Natura 2000 areas, preserve traditional orchards of fruit tree varieties, safeguard endangered genetic resources of plants and animals in agriculture, and enhance biodiversity in arable land. Subsidies for afforestation and creating field boundary woodlands, as well as service development for agriculture and forestry, are also included.

Support for the establishment and development of producer organizations and agricultural producer groups, marketing, and the development of cooperation related to food produced within quality systems is maintained. The Strategic Plan foresees the continuation of contributions to insurance for livestock animals and co-financing of mutual funds.

Among the key definitions within Polish legislation implementing the Strategic Plan of the CAP, "active farmer" and "agricultural activity" are noteworthy. An individual is automatically considered an active farmer if their direct payment amount for the preceding year does not exceed the equivalent of

5,000 euros in Polish złoty. Otherwise, an individual is regarded as actively farming if, as a general rule, they do not manage airports, administer water supply systems, administer permanent sports or recreational areas, provide railway transportation services, or engage in real estate transactions.

According to the adopted regulations, agricultural activity involves producing agricultural products through the breeding or rearing of animals for agricultural purposes or cultivating or rearing plants. Agricultural products refer to products listed in Annex I of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, excluding fishery products, as well as cotton cultivation and short rotation coppices. Agricultural activity also encompasses maintaining agricultural land in a condition suitable for grazing or cultivation without requiring preparatory actions beyond the use of common farming methods and equipment. If production is not taking place on a particular plot, for arable and permanent grassland, the farmer is obliged to perform at least one agrotechnical treatment aimed at removing or destroying undesirable vegetation. For orchards, the farmer must carry out at least two agrotechnical treatments, including one for the removal or destruction of undesirable vegetation and another for the removal of dead trees or branches or for the pruning of dry and withering branches, by July 31st of the year in which the application for aid was submitted.

5.4

In order to implement the regulation (EU) 2021/2115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 December 2021, the aforementioned Act of 8 February 2023 on the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for the years 2023-2027 was adopted in the Polish legal system. This act specifies tasks, authorities, and organizational units responsible for implementing the Strategic Plan, as well as the conditions and procedures for granting and disbursing financial assistance within the interventions covered by the Strategic Plan and under transitional national support referred to in Article 147 of Regulation 2021/2115, and technical assistance mentioned in Article 125 of Regulation 2021/2115. Additionally, it outlines the principles for implementing financial instruments in areas not specified in EU regulations or designated to be determined by the Member State of the European Union.

According to Article 19 of the mentioned Act, assistance is granted based on an agreement, unless the provisions of the act stipulate that assistance is granted by means of an administrative decision. Article 20 of this act states that assistance is granted by administrative decision for direct payments concerning basic income support, redistributive payments, payments for young farmers, payments related to production, payments under agri-environmental schemes, transitional national support, payments under environmental, climate-related, and other commitments in the field of management, Less Favored Areas (LFA) payments, support for forestry or afforestation investments, and risk management tools in the form of financial contributions towards insurance premiums, i.e., insurance premium subsidies.

One of the most significant legal regulations in the new CAP is the introduction of payments under agri-environmental schemes, which, as a component of direct payment systems, support the implementation of practices beneficial for the environment, climate, and animal welfare.

In Poland, agri-environmental schemes have been designed to promote practices that impact agricultural income by enhancing soil fertility, rational fertilization, and improving crop quality. The "carbon farming" agri-environmental scheme is particularly focused on this, allowing farmers to choose from eight available practices that best suit their needs.

6. External relations with third countries of the world

6.1

From the beginning of 2021 the UK has lost all the rights and obligations as a Member State and that it had during the transition period under the Withdrawal Agreement. It does not benefit from full access to the EU single market and customs union, as well as international agreements (including free trade agreements) that the EU has concluded with other third countries. This has created new barriers to trade in goods and to cross-border mobility.

On 30 December 2020, the Trade and Cooperation Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland was concluded.

To minimise the impact of the UK's exit from the EU, both parties have agreed to create a free trade area without tariffs or quotas. The agreement provides for market access liberalisation commitments for goods, including zero tariffs, zero quotas on all goods that have a documented origin. It also introduces modern solutions to minimise barriers to bilateral trade and guarantees close customs and regulatory cooperation. In addition to providing zero tariffs and quotas, the agreement also reduces administrative tariffs for services provided.

Nonetheless, trade with the UK after Brexit differs significantly from trade under the single market and the customs union. For example, all imports are subject to customs formalities and must comply with the regulations of the importing party. Imports into the EU must meet all EU standards and are subject to checks for safety, health and other public policy rules. It is also necessary to apply the rules of origin for goods to qualify for preferential trade conditions under the agreement.

From 1 January 2021, the controls and formalities required under EU law (in particular the Union Customs Code), including entry and exit summary declarations, apply to all goods entering or leaving the customs territory of the EU from the UK to the UK. Trade and customs formalities between the EU and Northern Ireland are carried out under the existing rules, in accordance with the Protocol on Ireland and Northern Ireland (contained in the UK's withdrawal agreement with the EU). The EU Customs Code and excise legislation is applied to goods entering and leaving Northern Ireland.

Both parties have agreed to mutually recognise 'Authorised Economic Operator' (AEO) status programmes for safety and security, enabling simplification and facilitation of customs controls. The agreement also replicates a number of mechanisms provided for in the EU Customs Code and UK customs legislation aimed at facilitating business.

One of the most important elements facilitating the cross-border movement of goods is the use of the Convention on a common transit procedure. It is also possible to apply the TIR Convention (Customs Convention on the International Transport of Goods under cover of TIR carnets). The agreement provides for innovative solutions concerning, for example, the use of the so-called Single Window, pre-arrival declarations before the arrival of goods at the border, or customs handling for roll on -roll off (ro-ro) traffic, i.e. ships carrying loaded trucks.

Import of animals, food and animal products from the UK into the EU

Upon expiration of the transitional period, i.e. from 1 January 2021, the import of animals and certain animal products and composite products, as well as animal feed into the EU from the UK, is subject to

border veterinary controls. This results in additional obligations, including the need to provide documentation proving that the relevant safety requirements are met (official certificates), the need to enter the consignment through designated border crossing points (BCPs), prenotification in TRACES.NT and notification for border control, etc.

The requirements and control procedures for goods imported from the UK to Poland will be analogous to those applied to other non-EU countries. They result from EU and national regulations.

Export of animals, food and animal products from the EU to the UK

Upon expiration of the transition period, i.e. from 1 January 2021, exports of animals and animal products and animal feed from the EU, including Poland, to the UK are subject to the requirements set by the UK side.

On 5 April 2023, an updated working version of the guide to new control procedures for UK trade with European Union countries - The Border Target Operating Model (TOM) - was published on UK government websites¹²².

Requirements for the importation into UK of products of animal origin subject to safety measures

From 1 January 2021, a veterinary certificate is required for the import of animal products subject to safety measures, which should be provided by the competent authority of the exporting country. In addition, the importer is required to pre-notify using the IPAFFS system and to provide the exporter with a number generated by this system. The exporter must enter the number provided in the commercial documentation or veterinary certificate (if required). In the event of an animal disease outbreak in the exporter's country, measures may be put in place to restrict the importation into the UK of products from the country concerned.

Requirements for the importation of animal by-products from the EU into the UK

From 1 January 2021, when importing high-risk animal by-products (HOPPs) from the EU into the UK, such as Category 1 material, Category 2 and meat and bone meal or animal fat derived from Category 1 and 2 materials and Category 3 processed animal protein (PAP), it is necessary:

- pre-authorisation by the importer from the UK Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA)/Animal and Plant Health Authority (APHA) for the importation of Category 1, and Category 2 material and meat and bone meal or animal fat derived from Category 1 and Category 2 materials;
- pre-notification by the importer through the IPAFFS system;
- goods (UPPZ) should be accompanied by up-to-date official commercial documentation.

From 1 January 2022, there is a requirement for pre-notification (prior notification) of cargoes with all plant and animal products by UK importers through the UK IPAFFS system.

Requirements for the importation of live animals from the EU into the UK

From 1 January 2021, the importation of live animals (including ornamental fish, equidae) and biological material from the EU requires:

- the use of export health certificates;

¹²² <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-border-target-operating-model-draft-for-feedback>.

- pre-notification (prior notification) by the importer through the UK IPAFFS system.

From 1 January 2021, EU-origin consignments can enter the UK at any point.

Are there any legal regulations concerning the promotion of agricultural products abroad, and to what extent?

Agriculture and agri-food exports are an important sector of the Polish economy. In 2019 Poland was the 15th largest exporter of agri-food products in the world and accounted for 2.1% of global and 5.9% of EU agricultural exports. Between 1999 and 2019, the value of exports of such products increased more than 12 times, with particularly rapid growth occurring after Poland's accession to the European Union. According to data from the Central Statistical Office (CSO) and the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MARD), from 2017 to 2020 it was €6.2 billion more, an increase of 22.2%. In 2017, the value of foreign sales reached €27.8 billion, while four years later (i.e. in 2021) it was already €37.4 billion. Trade in agri-food products plays an important role in Poland's trade exchange, and its importance has been growing since Poland's accession to the EU. In 2020, the share of agri-food exports in total exports was 14.3%, and the value of agri-food exports amounted to EUR 34.0 billion. This compares with a share of 13.5% in 2017.

The Polish agri-food sector is one of those branches of the national economy that achieves a positive balance in trade turnover. In total, between 2017 and 2021, the balance in agri-food trade reached EUR 53.1 billion. Poland's main partner in the export of these commodities has for many years been the countries of the European Union, with sales in this direction growing steadily. Their share in the export of agri-food products in 2019 was 81.6%, EUG countries 2.8% and EFTA countries 1.1%, while to other countries - 14.5%. Poland's main trading partners are Germany, the UK, the Netherlands, France, Italy and the Czech Republic.

In the conditions of high dependence of the market in Poland and agri-food exports on the market in the EU, which is characterised by low income elasticity of demand for food, the dynamics of agri-food exports to member states may weaken. Therefore, it has become necessary to look for new markets and develop trade with other markets in the world. For this reason, the promotion of agri-food products is becoming an increasingly important factor determining the growth of their exports and consumption.

In the Strategy for Responsible Development, adopted at the beginning of 2017 Strategy for Responsible Development, the agri-food sector - due to its export potential - was identified as one of the 12 strongest priority sectors of the economy. Food promotion is one of the key activities in the Foreign Expansion area of the Strategy for Responsible Development. The planned activities included the development and implementation of a system for promoting agri-food products and building a strong brand of Polish products under the slogan 'Poland tastes good'. The system envisaged the implementation of a targeted promotion policy to improve the competitiveness of Polish products on the global market and increase their export.

In November 2017 Minister of Agriculture adopted the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development's Food Promotion Strategy for 2017-2020¹²³. Its aim is to increase the competitiveness of Polish food products on foreign markets, as well as the recognisability of the Polish food brand at home and

¹²³ <https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo/strategia-promocji-zywnosci>.

abroad by shaping its positive image. Among other things, coherent rules of communication were defined, as well as priority directions for promotional activities. The Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development is the unit coordinating and supervising implementation of the Strategy, and the National Agricultural Support Centre (KOWR) was indicated as the main institution implementing promotion policy instruments in the agri-food sector. The brand of Polish food products was built at home and abroad under the common slogan and graphic symbol "Polska smakuje"/"Poland tastes good".

Are there impacts of WTO and EU provisions on the agriculture of the EU and individual Member States?

The EU's common trade policy is one of the areas in which the Union has full and exclusive competence. In other words, the EU acts in the WTO as a single entity represented by the Commission, not the Member States. On behalf of all of the Member States, the Commission negotiates trade agreements and defends EU interests before the WTO Dispute Settlement Body. The Commission regularly reports to and consults the Council and Parliament on the content of multilateral discussions and its strategy for conducting them. Under the Lisbon Treaty, the Council and Parliament are co-legislators and have the same right to decide on international trade issues.

Through the WTO, the EU also seeks to promote the use of a multilateral framework for trade negotiations to complement bilateral negotiations. The impasse in the Doha Round and the preference of other trading partners for bilateral agreements have forced the EU to partially revise its long-term strategy and return to bilateral and regional negotiations.

The obligations assumed by the EU within the WTO legal order, including bilateral agreements, have an impact on the shape of the Common Agricultural Policy and thus, of course, indirectly affect the situation of both Polish agricultural producers and domestic importers and exporters of agricultural products.

6.2

In a joint response to the current dramatic food situation resulting from Russia's aggression against Ukraine, WTO members agreed to exercise restraint on export restrictions and to exempt the World Food Programme humanitarian purchases from such restrictions.

In a joint Declaration on Food Security, WTO members committed to avoiding unjustified export restrictions on food and improving transparency on any export restrictions that do occur. Moreover, a Decision was taken to completely exempt humanitarian purchases for the World Food Programme from export restrictions. Agreement on this package shows that the WTO is ready to react to the exceptional circumstances that many members face in light of the reduced supply to world markets resulting from Russia's war against Ukraine and its blockage of Ukraine's grain exports.

Russia's military aggression against Ukraine has disrupted the continuity of food supplies to global markets. As part of the European Union's response to the Russian aggression against Ukraine, solidarity corridors between the EU and Ukraine were established to enable the export of Ukrainian agricultural products and trade with the country. In the initial period, however, these corridors did not function properly. This was only partly due to the fact that Poland had not previously been used as an important corridor for the export of Ukrainian agricultural products. As a result of a number of circumstances, according to various estimates, as much as 80% of Ukrainian cereals transported through Poland remained on the Polish market. Such a sharp increase in imports of Ukrainian cereals to the Polish market

caused tensions in that market. In response, the Polish government established a ban on the import of agricultural products from Ukraine (REGULATION OF THE MINISTER OF DEVELOPMENT AND TECHNOLOGY of 21 April 2023 on the ban on the import of agricultural products from Ukraine Dz.U. 2023/751). Pursuant to this regulation, a ban on the import of agricultural products listed in the Annex to this regulation originating in or imported from the territory of Ukraine into the territory of Poland was established until 30 June 2023. However, this prohibition did not apply to:

(1) external transit as referred to in Article 226 of Regulation (EU) No 952/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 October 2013 laying down the Union Customs Code (OJ L 269, 10.10.2013, p. 1, as amended), and

2) a common transit procedure based on the Convention on a common transit procedure drawn up in Interlaken on 20 May 1987 (OJ L 226, 13.08.1987, p. 2, as amended).- Official Journal of the European Union Special Edition, Chapter 2, Vol. 2, p. 291, as amended).

- provided that the transit is to end at seaports in Gdańsk, Gdynia, Świnoujście or Szczecin or outside the territory of the Republic of Poland.

The legality of the Polish government's solution from the perspective of EU law is questionable to say the least. Nevertheless, immediate action was taken at EU level. As a result, the European Commission reached an agreement with Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Romania and Slovakia on Ukrainian agri-food products. On 2 May 2023, temporary precautionary measures on agricultural products from Ukraine were introduced. The entry into force of the EU regulation meant that the previous national ban was repealed. For the time being, the safeguard measures introduced by Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/1100 of 5 June 2023 introducing preventive measures on certain products originating in Ukraine remain in force.

The basis for issuing this regulation was the existence of significant logistical difficulties. In particular, the infrastructure in Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Romania and Slovakia is still insufficient to cope with the sharp increase in traffic, especially at the borders between Ukraine and these Member States. These exceptional circumstances continue to affect the viability of local producers in the mentioned Member States. Consequently, exceptional circumstances affecting EU producers persist. In light of these circumstances, in the view of the European Commission, the current situation continues to justify action on the basis of Article 4(6) of Regulation (EU) 2023/1077.

Under this regulation it is permitted to release or place on the market or place under the customs warehousing procedure, the free zone procedure or the inward processing procedure the products originating in Ukraine listed in the annex to this regulation (wheat, maize, rapeseed, sunflower seeds) only on the territory of Member States other than Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Romania or Slovakia. However, the regulation does not restrict the possibility of transit of the indicated goods through the territories of the listed countries.